

Gendering the Academy
and Research: combating
Career Instability and Asymmetries

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Toward a Gendered Pipeline Typology: A Comparative Analysis Across Six European Countries

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In this report we propose a new Typology of Gendered Pipelines that provides a multi-level, multi-dimensional and comparative analytical framework of leaky pipelines and interrelated phenomena across six European countries and research institutions. Along with previous studies and with a number of contemporary European studies, the GARCIA project establishes that the moving away of women from the scientific or academic path, leading to higher positions does not happen so simply as one could imagine at first glance (Dubois-Shaik & Fusulier, 2016; Fassa et al., 2012; Le Feuvre, 2009; Grant et al., 2000), and that rather than adopting mono-causality, we have to take a more *composite view* of causes and effects when thinking about the “Leaky Pipeline” and other phenomena. When looking at gender policies, under the hood of “gender equality” these have so far also focussed in a rather epidermic way on improving figures and representations in professorships and leadership positions (albeit still without much effect). This has often resulted in policies that have targeted individuals in their personal trajectories through personal coaching rather than taking a larger picture on the systemic and organizational environment level of the pipelines (see WP3, WP4 and WP6 D 3.1; 4.2/4.3 and D 6.1/6.2). In short, research institutions more rarely question the *pipelines themselves*, although already broached by numerous research studies in different national contexts. Pipelines are often seen as either career trajectories, or organizational career pathways that point to “leaks”, which are undeniably present in all our case-study institutions (see Dubois-Shaik & Fusulier, 2015). However, we would argue that we cannot simply adopt an approach of “filling the gaps” or of pointing the fingers at gatekeepers. Alternately, our various project reports have fed the focus on the “leaky pipeline” in WP6 by providing us with a rich multi-level perspective (macro-level by looking at gender and welfare regimes, and comparative statistical data on leaky pipelines: WP3 and WP6 6.1 / meso-level by looking at organizational culture, structures and governance: WP4 and WP5 / micro-level by looking at experiences of early researchers and academics: WP4 and WP6; a multi-dimensional perspective (regimes, organizational systems, scientific fields, governing units, sex, gender, periods/stages of the career, work/life interference, relationships, power, cultures, contexts etc.); and a comparative perspective (across seven/six European countries, research institutions, SSH/STEM institutes, comparing women/men).

The reason why this WP6 combines the results from all the reports is that the various results enabled us to glean this more holistic and composite picture of the pipelines in contextualized case studies. The analytical process of each partner in WP6 enabled the collective realization that the “pipeline” is in fact a composite and complex structure. It is composed not only of career trajectories across individual people’s lives, but establishes that these are situated in a specific organizational context, in a specific institutional context and in a specific national and regional context. Cutting across all these contexts are also gender and welfare regimes, are new managerial regulations, are internationalization, are also professional networks and work cultures that cross national boundaries.

Moreover, we can underline how much the high level of uncertainty and precariousness of *early career researchers continuing in and moving away* from research and academia remains still an invisible issue in many European research institutions and universities, and that this fragility has been confirmed if not newly identified in our project. In Anglo-American research, the attention has been drawn to how research institutions are *gendered organizations* (Acker, 1990), which means that the social division of work between the sexes is translated in distinctive ways in structured institutions; in the principle of its organization, in the habits of work at the heart of the institution; in short in the practice of scientific work. However, we can now also safely speak about “**gendered pipelines**” with the multi-sense of “pipeline” as we now understand it. This report therefore is dedicated to a Typology of Gendered Pipelines.

In this report, we do not understand meta-analysis in a classic sense as a statistical comparative analysis, but rather as a particular composite analytical process of gleaning from the six case studies a typology of gendered pipelines that can serve institutions, researchers and policy makers to situate themselves and make a query into their own institutional, organizational and academic/research professional contexts. The form of typology we created looks at the specific *costs* of gendered pipelines, at three levels (macro/meso/micro). A first analytical step were the case-studies conducted and analysed by each partner in their respective contexts by looking at the leaky pipeline and interrelated phenomena through quantitative data (D 6.1), and through qualitative analysis using different data from different reports (D 6.2). A second step has been to create country case-study *vignettes* that are composed of these two levels of analyses and present a holistic mapping of leaky pipeline and interrelated phenomena in each case. Thirdly, these vignettes then have served

us in exposing some transversal results identified as significant and recurring cross-country trends. We demonstrate how this transversal analysis points to features of leaky pipeline phenomena related to scientific/academic careers that appear *despite national and institutional contexts*. In a fourth step, from these overall key characteristics, we draw up a typology of gendered pipelines, which is gleaned from a comparative analysis that was undertaken across the six country case studies (vignettes). This is a comparison of the different case-studies of Garcia beneficiaries and of studying recurring configurations that assemble certain features and characteristics, such as specific gender and welfare regimes, specific quantitative statistical features of careers, key narrative results relating to visible gendered and work dynamics, certain recruitment criteria that are discursive resources and organizational modalities. From this comparative analysis, we propose a typology, with a table of costs that allows identifying a *range of costs* of gendered pipelines on three entity levels (macro/meso/micro) as an innovate and new Typology comprising three Types of Gendered Pipelines:

- Type (1) “Persisting in precariousness” career path and “Mandarin” organisation with High cumulative costs;
- Type (2) “Persisting in uncertainty and ambivalence” career path and “University institution” organizational model with Moderate level costs;
- Type (3) “Winning in competition” career path and “market-driven” organization with Specific Costs.

If the Type (1) has been mainly deduced from the Italian and Slovenian cases, the Type (2) from the Belgian and Icelandic cases, and the Type (3) from the Netherlands and Swiss cases, this typology is not a classification of countries and institutions, but more a typology of rationales (meta).

In terms of key results, we have identified a common foundation of interrelated phenomena across all case studies. More importantly however, we have identified that these common interrelated phenomena appear despite, or because of specific contextual, organisational and configurational compositions. What we can discern is that this composition is quite significant in identifying the level and range of costs that leaky pipelines can incur upon the three entity levels. And that there are significant differences in the interstructuralization of these compositions that generate different kinds, levels and range of costs. Importantly, there are clear indications, inferred from the idea of costs that institutions can counteract towards reducing these cumulative and specific costs, and that they take their share in responsibilities about career opportunities and what becomes more significant, in the organizing of work.

In terms of gender balance and inequality, on the individual level, we can identify how in the Type (1), women have a very precarious overall situation, which shows high risk-and precipice in order to continue upon this linear career path, with a lot of personal costs (health, maternity, professional development, stabilization, recognition) and less possibilities and opportunities for rebounding or for catching the fall. We can speak about a high degree of gender inequality for early career women researchers/academics, compared to their male peers. In the Type (2), in terms of gender inequality, balancing is more difficult to achieve for women compared to their male counterparts. In this type, there is more ambiguity and a harder to achieve precarious balance, with the need of the “right” configurations, which are harder to come by for women than for their male peers. In the Type (3) women early researchers and academics have a harder time juggling with many things at the same time than their male counterparts; like in the Type (2), there is a hard to achieve balance between work and family life, with overwork and omnipresence in a exclusive and elitist organization.

What this analysis has shown is that this gender inequality impacts upon the macro level of science as much as upon the institution within which it is based. On the level of science as a collaborative, collective work and product of an organization, we can see repercussions that have a significant impact upon the balance that arguably needs to be achieved between the key underlying priorities, missives and motivations of science. For example, important scientific exchanges and development between teaching and research may suffer, as teaching is undervalued and experienced as a sticky floor both on institutional levels and on the level of the individual researchers. This devaluing of teaching moreover is parallel to a rising number of students in the very same institutions, where per student-teacher ratio is lower. This means that on the institutional level, there is a bid for students, without a real thought given about the teaching body and its stabilization, motivation, assistance, training etc. This decoupled way of organizing teaching and research can therefore have important outcomes. There is also an increased short-term research and knowledge production with the rise

of short-term research contracts, fraught with limits in time dedicated to fundamental research, coupled with a lesser governmental funding of fundamental research. Early researchers and academics spend also a lot of time bidding for external funding, making the competition more stringent between them, but also making less time for developing research works. Arguably, this reduces the depth of research undertaken, as researchers/academics juggle with more deadlines and hyper productivity in terms of publications. The temporariness of research affects the quality of research outputs and the type of knowledge elaborated in academia.

In all three types of gendered pipelines, there grows a large number of non-stabilized, “floating” not fully integrated research body and assistantship teaching staff, with lesser social and pension schemes in the Type (1), and which are not recognized.

We are also looking at lesser diversity in research and teaching in terms of gender, with fewer female role models, and the overall persistence of masculine-based scientific research work model, despite the feminisation of higher education in all three Types of organizations. The institutions can ask themselves whether this model really mirrors what kind and form of scientific knowledge they are producing. In the Type (3), research and teaching continues to be produced by an elite, more homogenous group of researchers/academics, continuing the Ivory Tower effect. In all three types, we can also speak about brain drain for academia and other sectors, because although there has been a feminised higher education, there remain little career chances in academia and also simultaneously little conversion of PhD in SSH sectors outside of academia in the labour market of the Type (1). In the Types (2) and (3), the extra academic labour market is more open to highly skilled workers, male and female, but without a real recognition of the PhD level. This raises questions about a decrease in the purpose and value of the PhD, whereby increasing number of doctoral and postdoctoral researchers are recruited.

Moreover, the persisting gender stereotypes in STEM and SSH in all three Types continues to raise questions. Institutions, research and teaching units can benefit by rethinking their purposes of their degrees, their doctoral and postdoctoral appointments, with more responsible and long term vision in making choices, promoting, fostering and guiding strategically.

The Type (1) institution and scientific community are arguably contributing to produce a contradiction between work and family, as women struggle to keep up family and careers, renouncing to parenthood more than men. This is paired with no effective childcare and elderly support system in society at large, and not taken into consideration upon the institutional level. In the Type (2) and (3), we can see the appearance of parental ambiguity, with women having a harder time to keep the balance, with a high dependence upon the right configurations, and feelings of guilt at work and off work. The vertical glass ceiling the higher we climb, which persists in all three types, but especially in Type (3) shows how “keeping up the balance” depends on a high number of favourable configurations that are very hard to come by for women, making the progression in the career as arduous as entering it, especially for professorship, full professorship, management and leadership positions.

We can see overall for all types, the high significance of funding systems upon gender inequality, and for all three entity levels. Due to the type of funding systems (point- and closed envelop systems), students are attracted due to a bid for governmental funding, which reinforces a competition over collaboration culture for units and amongst individuals. Moreover, women early researchers and academics have a harder time obtaining funding. In all three types, there is a lesser teacher/student ratio, and more degrees are being given, with lesser quality of teaching programmes. There is lesser governmental funding, especially in SSH (see per student funding for SSH and STEM). We can also say that scientific production is governed by funding structures, because there is lesser fundamental research, and lesser funding for SSH research and teaching.

One major element that plays strongly upon creating costs on all three levels are the gaps between formal and informal criteria, not in terms of their existence, but in terms of tensions of visibility, of clarity, of demands, of discursive resources and making sense of work. There is in all three types, an institutional ambivalence and discrepancy of what can be called formal, or competition-based, or internationally orientated criteria, and of informal, subjective, local nomination-based or integration-based criteria for nomination during recruitment procedures. The struggle for women in this is a balance between the rock and a hard place, because the formal criteria are often hyper productivity (high-ranking, numerous publications) and mobility based, which are difficult for women to keep up with during childbearing and -rearing years. Moreover, they are difficult because publication systems are often intimately linked to network access and possibilities of authorship,

both of which are reduced for female early researchers. The second type of criteria that are more local or institutional are strongly linked to access to institutional knowledge, codes, networks (both national and international) and gatekeepers/mentors. This again is a configuration that is less often achieved for early career researchers that are women, as we are also looking at the existence of cooptation logics, lesser female role models and mentors, less support. For career progression moreover, there is the importance of local embeddedness and an overall institutional (all-round academic) implication, omnipresence that is more difficult for women, except with again the “right” configurations coming together (institutional support, private support).

This report offers a multi-level, multi-dimensional and comparative analysis and Typology, that would allow institutions to situate themselves in a table of different recurring costs on three levels (Science/Institution/Individual), and would permit conceiving gender action plans, and work action plans that are geared toward a holistic organizational and pipeline analysis, status quo evaluation and projecting interrelated actions.

1. INTRODUCTION

The diverse results and analytical processes in this project have enabled us to *redefine a new approach of tackling questions about the “Leaky pipeline” and other interrelated phenomena*, such as “glass ceiling”, “sticky floor”, “Matilda- and Matthew effects” amongst others (see D 6.1 and 6.2 reports). The more classic perspective draws the picture that often “promising” women fall out of scientific and academic careers after their PhDs and that it is presumed that “everything happens in these professional trajectories to make them leave as though it would be some kind of auto-elimination, a chain of decisions taken more or less consciously, but always freely, by young women, who decide to do something else rather than a scientific career (maternity, family life, following their spouses to another country for his job, etc.) (Beaufays and Kraiss, 2005:52/53). Other studies also often focus on how certain fields are still underrepresented by either sex and that traditional gender stereotypes persist in fields such as STEM for women or SSH for men (Blickenstaff, 2005), tracing back the backlogs of suffering motivations or gendered tracking during early (primary school) and latter (secondary and higher) educational trajectories. Yet other more contemporary research speaks about gender discrimination in recruitment, where women are systematically under selected for permanent academic positions and for promotions in higher leadership positions (Morley, 2013; Benschop and Brink, 2012). However, along with these previous studies and with a number of contemporary European studies, the GARCIA project can establish that the moving away of women from the scientific or academic path, leading to higher positions does not happen so simply as one could imagine at first glance (Dubois-Shaik & Fusulier, 2016; Fassa et al., 2012; Le Feuvre, 2009; Grant et al., 2000), and that rather than adopting mono-causality, we have to take a more **composite view** of causes and effects when thinking about the “Leaky Pipeline” and other phenomena.

We would like to underline that more traditional gender policies, under the hood of “gender equality”, have so far also focussed in a rather epidermic way on improving figures and representations in professorships and leadership positions (albeit still without much effect). This has often resulted in policies that have targeted individuals in their personal trajectories through personal coaching rather than taking a larger picture on the systemic and organizational environment level of the pipelines (see WP3, WP4 and WP6 D 3.1; 4.2/4.3 and D 6.1/6.2). In short, research institutions more rarely question the *pipelines themselves*, although already broached by numerous research studies in different national contexts. Pipelines are often seen as either career trajectories, or organizational career pathways that point to “leaks”, which are undeniably present in all our case-study institutions (see Dubois-Shaik & Fusulier, 2015). However, we would argue that we cannot simply adopt an approach of “filling the gaps” or of pointing the fingers at gatekeepers. Alternately, our various project reports have fed the focus on the “leaky pipeline” in WP6 by providing us with a rich

- **multi-level perspective:** macro-level by looking at gender and welfare regimes, and comparative statistical data on leaky pipelines: WP3 and WP6 6.1 / meso-level by looking at organizational culture, structures and governance: WP4 and WP5 / micro-level by looking at experiences of early researchers and academics: WP4 and WP6;
- **multi-dimensional perspective:** regimes, organizational systems, scientific fields, governing units, sex, gender, periods/stages of the career, work/life interference, relationships, power, cultures, contexts etc.;
- and a **comparative perspective** across six European countries, research institutions, SSH/STEM institutes, comparing women/men.

The reason why this WP6 combines the results from all the reports is that the various results enabled us to glean this more holistic and composite picture of the pipelines in contextualized case studies. The analytical process of each partner in WP6 enabled the collective realization that the “pipeline” is in fact a composite and complex structure. It is composed not only of career trajectories across individual people’s lives, but establishes that these are situated in a specific organizational context, in a specific institutional context and in a specific national and regional context. Cutting across all these contexts are also gender and welfare regimes, are new managerial regulations, are internationalization, are also professional networks and work cultures that cross national boundaries.

Moreover, we can underline how much the high level of uncertainty and precariousness of *early career researchers continuing in and moving away* from research and academia remains still an

invisible issue in many European research institutions and universities, and that this fragility has been confirmed if not newly identified in our project. In Anglo-American research, the attention has been drawn to how research institutions are *gendered organizations* (Acker, 1990), which means that the social division of work between the sexes is translated in distinctive ways in structured institutions; in the principle of its organization, in the habits of work at the heart of the institution; in short in the practice of scientific work. However, we can now also safely speak about “**gendered pipelines**” with the multi-sense of “pipeline” as we now understand it.

A first analytical step were the case-studies conducted and analysed by each partner in their respective contexts by looking at the leaky pipeline and interrelated phenomena through quantitative data (D 6.1), and through qualitative analysis using different data from different reports (D 6.2). A second step has been to create country case-study *vignettes* (Italy, Belgium, The Netherlands, Iceland Switzerland, Slovenia) that are composed of these two levels of analyses and present a holistic mapping of leaky pipeline and interrelated phenomena in each case (find vignettes in Appendix). Thirdly, these vignettes then have served us in exposing some transversal results identified as significant and recurring cross-country trends. We demonstrate how this transversal analysis points to features of leaky pipeline phenomena related to scientific/academic careers that appear *despite national and institutional contexts*. In a fourth step, from these overall key characteristics, we draw up a typology of gendered pipelines, which is gleaned from a **comparative analysis** that was undertaken across the six country case studies (vignettes). This is a comparison of the different case-studies of Garcia beneficiaries and of studying recurring configurations that assemble certain features and characteristics, such as specific gender and welfare regimes, specific quantitative statistical features of careers, key narrative results relating to visible gendered and work dynamics, certain recruitment criteria that are discursive resources and organizational modalities (see Appendix: Italy, Belgium, The Netherlands, Iceland, Switzerland, Slovenia).

From this comparative analysis, we propose a typology that allows identifying a **range of costs of gendered pipelines on three entity levels (macro/meso/micro)** that will be specified.

In the first part, we explain the specificity of our meta-analysis approach. In this report, we do not understand meta-analysis in a classic sense as a statistical comparative analysis, but rather as a particular composite analytical process of gleaning from the six case studies two forms of typologies of gendered pipelines that can serve institutions, researchers and policy makers to situate themselves and make a query into their own institutional, organizational and academic/research professional contexts.

2. TOWARD A GENDERED PIPELINE TYPOLOGY

In our previous quantitative and qualitative reports on the leaky pipeline and interrelated phenomena, we presented the individual case-studies of each of the six research and academic institutions (Universities and other research institutions). These reports comprised on the one hand a careful analysis of quantitative figures pertaining to the numbers and percentages of women and men in both the national levels in different professional sectors, situating thus the scientific sector within the national trends on gender distributions, and also pertaining to organizational indicators that map throughout several years (roughly between 2009-2014) the distribution of women and men in different levels of the scientific/academic career ladders. This quantitative report contributed in gaining a cross-country picture and the confirmation of existing leaky pipeline phenomena (Berryman, 1983; Alper, 1993), and of further interrelated and intimately associated phenomena, such as the glass ceiling effect (Hymowitz, Schellhardt, 1986; Fassa, Kradolfer, 2010), the sticky floor (Booth, Francesconi and Frank, 2003) and the bottle neck located at the doctoral and postdoctoral level, the latter of which remained until now largely unexplored (see Dubois-Shaik and Fusulier 2015). Although some of these conclusions are not new in terms of findings from previously conducted studies, a multi-level and interpretative analysis of conditions, modalities, gender and welfare regimes, policies and configurations of scientific/academic careers in the six (seven) different Garcia contexts (Italy, Belgium, The Netherlands, Iceland Switzerland, Slovenia (and Austria for D6.1 only) has enabled us to underpin **some significant tendencies in the way scientific/academic careers are organized, embedded and conceived**. These may be jointly and interrelatedly contributing to the kind of gendered configurations that are visible in all country and institutional cases, despite the various differences across national and organizational contexts. These interrelated results have certainly underlined the importance of changing the analytical

perspective upon the leaky pipeline by looking at the Garcia institutions as *gendered organizations* (Acker, 1990), rather than merely tracing and locating the “leaks” (Beaufays and Kraiss, 2005).

This change in perspective was further complemented by a thorough qualitative narrative analysis, which provided a comprehensive overview of the leaky pipeline in the different contexts of six Garcia beneficiaries. It is based on more than two hundred interviews in total (men and women in SSH and in STEM research fields) conducted among **three target sub-groups: movers/leavers** (people moved to other research institution/people having left research/academia altogether), **postdocs**, and **newly tenured researchers/academics**. This sample was chosen with a hypothesis that early career researchers/academics represent a particularly precarious and jeopardized stage within the scientific career path and unexplored population within research organizations. This precariousness was primarily confirmed through the quantitative results from D6.1, notably through locating the bottleneck at the postdoctoral level in nearly all country cases. Based on the various further results across countries and institutions, we draw the conclusion that this hypothesis is confirmed and that early stage/career researchers and academics are noteworthy groups of workers at risk, the results of which raise many questions about the “leaky” pipeline(s). Each national case shows the interrelated mechanisms operating in the leaky pipeline phenomena that were gleaned from the narrative data across different early stages of the career; a confirmation of the co-optation logic, or of the existence of mobilizing masculinities that works through important gatekeepers (Benshop and Brink, 2012); a cumulative Matthew (Merton, 1969) and Matilda effect (Rossiter, 1995 ; Fassa et al., 2012); a paradoxical sticky floor (Booth et al., 2003) for undervalued tasks, including teaching; different rapports towards work and private life interference (Fusulier and Drancourt, 2015; Fusulier and Del Rio Carral, 2012; Crompton, 1999); and last but not least an intensely experienced and factual bottleneck at the postdoctoral level with the difficulty to obtain permanent positions or tenureship. A significant set of questions were answered by looking at how movers (persons who moved on to other research or academic positions in other research institutions) or leavers (persons who changed their careers and sectors) experienced their work in the Garcia institutions and what their reasons/motivations were for moving/leaving. This provided us with further insights about how work and organization are translated in a gendered way, and confirmed the interrelated phenomena working jointly upon different leaky pipelines (see Dubois-Shaik and Fusulier 2015).

These various reports enable us to identify the *complex and multivariable nature of the pipeline(s)* on the one hand. On the other hand the reports evoke how much the social division of work between the sexes is indeed *translated in distinctive ways in its structured institutions*; in the *gender and welfare regimes* within which the institution is embedded and by which its *work ethos and culture* is invariably shaped; in the *principle of its organisation*, influenced by external and internal *pressures and discourses*; the kind of *policy responses* it draws forth to tackle these phenomena; in the *habits of research/academic work*; the *specificities of scientific fields, sectors and institutes* (SSH, STEM); the *discursive resources* (Kuhn, 2006) that are mobilized by actors when making sense (Weick, 1997) of their work¹; and not least, the *modalities of careers* at the heart of the institution. The gender dynamics that operate amidst these different mechanisms at play therefore not only reflect or change external societal and socio-economic trends, but also contribute in enhancing, reproducing or reinforcing certain gender regimes, work ethics and culture, discourses, and organizational structure/modes of functioning. This in turn shapes career modalities in particular gendered ways.

In this report, we would aim at proposing a distinctive analytical way of addressing the complexity of the leaky pipeline phenomena, composed of the different variables enlisted above. We would enlarge the perspective upon the pipeline to not only adopt a *trajectory perspective*, but also a *contextual, organizational and configurational perspective*; in short of redefining leaky pipelines as *gendered pipelines*. In a first step, we have written a **vignette** of each Garcia case (see Appendix), by looking closely at A) the national gender and welfare regimes, B) previously existing gender policies, C) the quantitative analysis of the leaky pipeline, including the national and organizational quantitative data, D) the qualitative narrative data from interviews with three sub-groups; movers/leavers, postdocs and newly tenured researchers/academics, E) recruitment and discursive resources¹ and F) organizational modalities. These vignettes allow us to establish connections

¹ With respect to recruitment processes, we would argue that the norms of careers and professional practices are shaped by discourses (Fairclough, 2009; Kuhn, 2006), in the sense of “référentiels” (Muller, 2006), that are both constructing and constructed by actors’ (both women’ and men’) hierarchical articulation, in a process of sensemaking (Weick, 1995) of their work. This process includes referencing of an array of discursive resources (Kuhn, 2006) in their everyday professional and personal/family lives, which constitutes an important form of identity work (Antaki and Widdicombe, 1998; Jenkins, 1996; Kuhn, 2006). This sensemaking (Weick, 1995) process, we argue, shapes institutional

between the different reports (D6.1, D6.2, D5.1, D3.1, D7.2²) that were realized for each theme and for each partner, whereby we interpret the results from each vignette through the lens of the gendered pipeline, proposing a new Typology.

For this Typology, we have gleaned from the six country vignettes particular features that emerge as specific configurations and combinations of the different elements of the vignettes. This enabled us to identify **three different types of “career paths and organizations”**. We argue that specific types of career paths are often in juxtaposition with, or co-shaped by specific types of organizations. We therefore combine the type of career path with a type of organization.

This typology would allow us to situate the different career paths and organizations, not in a scale of more or less “leaks” of persons leaving the careers, but rather in *what is at stake for different levels of the pipelines, in other words what are “the costs”*. Without adhering too closely to social exchange theorists, by costs, we would understand the “price to pay” or the challenge for a certain orientation, perspective, objective or underlying principle of an entity that operates upon the pipeline. This entity we would locate at three levels;

- a) the **macro level of science as an entity**, not with a big S, but rather science as a collaborative, collective work and product of an organization (Latour and Woolgar, 1986);
- b) the **meso level of the institution** as a working, interacting and operational entity with particular common institutional missions;
- c) the **micro individual level of a worker and composite being** as an entity.

These three entities have a competing and complementary relationship with each other over their underlying principles, objectives and motivations.

Our three entities of macro-/meso-/and micro levels (Science/Institution/Individual) that are involved in shaping and operating scientific/academic careers and organizations have their own share of particular, self-defined purposes and principles. We create a table, which shows the **interplay of these three types of “career paths and organizations” with the three levels of entities (Science/Institution/Individual) and the range and level of costs in each**. The three types of career paths and organizations show how these three different entities interplay with different guiding principles, which can generate different types and levels of costs with respect to what is deemed important to each entity. In short, the three types of career paths and organizations show different range and level of costs. We cannot speak about costs, without also referring to benefits; some configurations and interplay between entities also can bring advantages or satisfaction to each entity according to its own guiding principles, objectives and motivations. In our analysis we focus on costs however, to enable institutions, policy makers and researchers/academics to map their own contexts and to construct some tailored action plans.

We can speak about *the level of costs* that the particular academic/scientific career involves: the level of costs that the institutional and organizational conditions, demands and work culture/organization involves; the level of costs that science as a product and overall missive of research and teaching involves. To give a concrete example: On the individual level, for instance, we can speak about

- the choices that are possible for reconversion of the doctorate or flexibility within the career;
- or the compatibility and balance that is possible at the level of working/private life;
- or at the level of gaining career stability, institutional membership, professionalization and progression.

We can speak about the how some types of gendered pipelines, with their specific configurations, require more costs at the individual level and perhaps also at the institutional level and organizational level. Higher costs on all three levels may also mean that the institutional mechanisms

and professional practices and feeds on, as much as from discourses in different work locales (Pred, 1990; Keenoy and Oswick, 2003) or local orders (Friedberg, 1997). The discursive resources that emerge from the analyses of qualitative data on how actors make sense of their work were identifiable amongst others as those pertaining to “how to advance in the career”. These discursive resources therefore are largely oriented towards recruitment criteria and are negotiated amidst a range of competing requirements for career progression, personal development/satisfaction and institutional membership (see D7.2).

2 All the reports are available at the webpage http://garciaproject.eu/?page_id=52

and structures contribute to a high degree to the individual choice and wellbeing level and to gender inequality. Lower costs on one or the other level may also mean more benefits for one or for all levels. An important part of reading costs is that they can represent different impacts upon gender dynamics. Thus, we can deduce, from our table, **how costs affect the gender balance and inequality** in the different types of gendered pipeline configurations and institutions.

The idea of these three types of “career paths and organizations” with different cost configurations would allow specific research institutions to situate themselves, in order to determine what this means in terms of their own leaky pipeline situations, their three entity levels and their relationships and what costs are at stake. Le Feuvre (2005) underlines how important it is for institutions to clearly define the model of feminisation that they want to promote in academia, since different typological processes can have contrasting effects on the degree to which the existing gender system is reproduced, reconfigured or transformed. This “cost” Typology can assist institutions and individuals in determining gender policies and measures, which are not uni-dimensional and take into consideration a host of interacting costs.

3. TRANSVERSAL FEATURES ACROSS THE SIX COUNTRY VIGNETTES

Snapshot

In terms of gender, it is clear: there is an important *masculine habitus* (Bourdieu, 1984) confirmed for all six case-studies. In all cases, *parenthood* tips the scale of experiencing difficulty to reconcile career and personal life, whereby SSH has more parents, but STEM are still few to rare, especially before tenureship. There is in most cases a persisting gender stereotype in STEM, which remains male dominated. In most cases, *linear pathways* are favoured, with many “*lonely heroes and heroines*” in many contexts. There is some *sexism*, especially in STEM and *gender bias*. In all cases there is the experience of early career researchers and academics of *overwork and omnipresence* (all-consuming). The configurations of the couple and the support from partner and others in ones’ entourage, especially the *assistance of networks and mentors is considered essential* in being able to subscribe to work requirements and demands, whereby *women in all cases generally receive less support in all these quarters*. There is an overall emphasis in all institutional cases of “*competition*” over *collaboration*, which makes institutional embeddedness and team work a challenge, especially for early career women.

Gender and Welfare Regimes

There remain in most leaky pipeline configurations a traditional to modified traditional male breadwinner models (one-and-a-half-earner); whereby either female academic employment is less present, and moreover a part-time character is not compatible with the masculine habitus and structure of academic careers, or even research careers with an emphasis upon hyper productivity and omnipresence (the requirement of being available and physically present for the three missives of university; teaching, research, service to the institution and society, to which we must add an important time and space dedicated to administrative work/auto-management). There is an overall trend of full-time work in academia. Motherhood is considered in most cases incompatible, and when motherhood occurs there is a high parental ambivalence (difficulty reconciling work and family and increased feelings of guilt and being divided amongst the two) for women.

Gender Policy

Although there are some cases with no implementation of gender policy and more only on the discursive level, even those countries with some gender implementation policy focus mainly on the doctoral level and seem to be lacking on the postdoc level. The type of financial measures and quota introduction focus upon hyper productivity-based criteria, which in its turn may not really help women early researchers/academics. There is overall in all country cases little support on the level of teaching (devalued, sometime defined as sticky floor or academic housework) and on the level of effects on gender through budgeting.

Quantitative Data

In terms of the leaky pipeline phenomena we have more or less similar results for all countries, the existence of the scissor-shaped curve, confirming a leaky pipeline every case. The common features being:

- ***A massification of students and feminisation in higher education***, with exceptions in STEM.

Having an important study body is often the prerequisite for the distribution of governmental subsidies and budget allocations for universities in many countries (see also Garcia WP 5.1 report on gender budgeting). It remains therefore an important facet of competition between research institutions. Moreover, the “Bologna system” in European Union has also allowed a transferability and mobility of students from different sectors and higher education colleges, also with an ever-growing international student body. At the same time, the access to PhD has risen – here too research institutions try to obtain a maximum number of doctorates – with growing numbers of ongoing PhDs, however with lesser women (and men) actually obtaining PhD, which points to some particular yet under-explored difficulties to be located during this period. An important result obtained is that postdocs and assistant researchers with non-permanent contracts are significantly rising in numbers, and institutions are hosting a growing number of temporary researchers. One key problem with this kind of massification at these levels of study and posts is that the number of permanent academic posts and higher education positions are not equivalent or rising in proportion to rising number of PhDs and postdocs, especially in SSH, where the mobility to other sectors is less possible and higher education remains a major job sector. In STEM, the mobility to other sectors, such as industry, remains still an attractive and real feature for many students and PhDs, although the value of the doctorate is not always equivalent in terms of recognized skills, status and pay, as can be observed in the different national case studies. A response by research institutions and mainly of national governments to this rise in massification is a means of introducing some filters as well as selective opportunities, such as an introduction of research funding, or prizes attributed to excellent research or grants (Switzerland, Slovenia, Iceland, Belgium, Netherlands, Austria). However, tying in with the difficulties that are addressed in the Garcia WP7.1 report (Herschberg et al. 2015), on the types of excellence standards and the criteria for selection for gaining access to research projects as well as permanent posts (CV body building, production, competition, merit on numbers of publications and so on), these are found not to be very conducive or less realistic for women to realize in the periods of doctorates and postdocs, an age group normally dedicated to family building or potential motherhood. So although gender equality is sometimes featured in the types of research funding, the nature of selection criteria remains largely the same, more male orientated. Achieving these kinds of research funding and prize are therefore still conceived in a particular type of profile, which require a high level of engagement, CV building and dense work practice, often not inclusive of other aspects of life, such as family, care and social life.

- ***A bottleneck with different intensities and slightly different points, after PhD or during/after postdoc.***

- ***Tensions in the value, purpose and status of the doc/postdoc on the labour market.***

From the different country reports, it also becomes visible that the value, purpose and status of doctorate and postdoctorate is fraught with some important tensions, which we would argue would contribute to the precariousness of this stage. In most countries and institutional cases the scientific value or purpose of the doctorate and postdoc therefore continues to constitute part of the real practical requirements of the research and academic career. It can be argued that this has its rightful continuity, as the actual purpose of a doctorate is to develop, deepen and widen your research content and field and to undertake a profound examination of a given topic, which would enable you to “become” an able researcher and expert. The postdoctoral purpose would originally perhaps consolidate the doctoral period, both in terms of your field, specialization and gaining a certain independence in conducting research. However, the reality shows an increasing and significant tension between the scientific and formative value of the PhD and postdoc as opposed to the job market value on two levels: firstly, increasingly docs and postdocs are taking on the place of temporary job opportunities and employees within the research institutions. They provide research institutions with funding contracts, projects and also increasingly a cheap source of teaching staff. There is also a feminization in the teaching corps, which concerns mainly the lowest levels of the academic ladder: the assistants and other non- defined or permanent status of the scientific corps (notably postdocs, or PhD holders without permanent posts). However, this ever growing crowd of

PhDs and postdocs are not given any institutional permanence or affiliation, sometimes even classified as administrative and technical staff (see UNIL, Switzerland).

Research institutions (as well as government orientations and funding) are increasingly operating as tenders for temporary positions without any obligations as employers: we could be speaking about a loss of employership of research institutions, while increasingly subscribing to entrepreneurship. The contradiction arises in that in institutional practices for career advancement, doctorate and postdoctorate, even in funding practices (Belgium, Switzerland, Netherlands) are seen as a scientific “rite of passage”, a necessary formation or limited period of passage before moving on: however, as jobs are slim and not available, postdoctoral periods have become longer and become job contracts, with no real status (and power) within the institution. Hence once again the idea of “invisible” labour force that constitutes no institutional obligations, simply contributions that go largely unaccounted for. This has gendered configurations, as women are increasing in these temporary contracts.

- **There is a common “ratchet effect”;** you gain as an early researcher the doctoral degree for life, however, whilst gaining a permanent tenured position there persists for women some uncertainty about career progression, despite the assurance of being able to continue a scientific/academic career, there continue to be some symbolic and recognition-based hurdles to cross; and they are not free from material conditions and configurations.

- **A perceived sticky floor on the level of teaching.** Paired with the qualitative results, this sticky floor is experienced and perceived by early researchers and undervalued by institutions; teaching itself is not seen as gratifying, often taken for gaining access to permanent positions, and if taken voluntarily, then not recognized sufficiently. For newly tenured, teaching tasks are seen to diminish research and contribute to overwork.

- **Gender regimes, work/life balance and work ethics are similar in greedy institutions.**

According to the findings in D3.1 (Le Feuvre 2015) and also D5.1 (Steinthorsdottir et al. 2016), the problem of articulating work and family within a gender regime maintaining a sexual division of productive and reproductive work is one of the apparent causes of the downfall in terms of leaky pipeline. For example the Swiss case speaks of a “modified male breadwinner” model, with extremely high childcare costs, high levels of horizontal and vertical segregation, a relatively large gender pay gap, particularly at the upper reaches of the occupational hierarchy. Similarly, the Dutch case speaks about a one-and-a-half-earner model: the most dominant working arrangement of (heterosexual) couples in the Netherlands is a situation in which the man has a full-time job, and the woman a part-time job. This situation is more often true when couples have children. Most Garcia case study countries denote high levels of women’s part-time working, particularly amongst mothers of young children. Therefore, the division of domestic labour and unpaid care activities remains unequal in most if not all of the Garcia countries, with women taking responsibility for almost 80% in some country cases of daily household chores (Slovenia). However, despite the part-time character of female work upon the general labour market, women with a university degree tend to work much more often in full-time jobs. The same goes for women working in the research/academic sector. Yet, female assistant and associate professors work much less often than their male colleagues in full-time positions. At the same time, the gender difference for full-time jobs is small at the level of full professorship. It could be argued that climbing the scientific/academic career ladder does not permit part-time character, thus also requiring a full-time presence or work the higher you climb. There remains an explained gender pay gap in most country cases.

Another argument in terms of work ethics influenced by external and internal work regimes is the existence of a particular organizational logic or culture, whereby interrelated phenomena to leaky pipelines and glass ceiling are produced. There is an ever increasing workload transferred to individuals, which necessitates high demands of institutional commitment, not only in terms of political or governing involvement of individuals alongside their main work of research and teaching, but also an important increase in logistic, governance and administrative tasks, and of finding own funds, which research centres and faculties are not able to supply in sufficient amounts. There is a form of entrepreneurship (self-regulation and funding) required on unit-and individual level, without adhering to managerialism (see Belgian case). Parallely to this we can count in the effects of the university as a greedy institution (Coser, 1974; Grant et al., 2000; Hendrickson et al., 2011; del Rio Carral, Fusulier, 2013) in that research and teaching demands are today increasing in complexity and availability of the researcher/academic: the researcher/academic needs to be entirely invested in his work. According to Ule (2002) referred to in the Slovenian analysis, academic institutions are —

at least for the matter of power, influence, prestige, reputation and money— still social spaces strongly determined by specific masculine academic culture in which two types of characters prevail. One refers to a scientist fully engaged just in his professional work but anything else, and the other one to a scientist manager who in informal male networks negotiates the sharing of research money, positions and division of power and authority in science. In both these profiles, female scientists hardly can situate themselves.

Qualitative Narrative Data

Qualitative data also reveal some similarities between the different case-studies.

- Postdocs: Mentors' roles are crucial, whereby the narratives are very varied, depending on experience with mentors; overall, women have less supportive relationships. Those who are successful emphasize the role of a supportive mentor.
- Postdoctoral narratives are more homogenous, newly tenured somewhat mixed, with overwork and omnipresence and parenthood being significant for all cases, but satisfaction levels are different depending on case; for example how teaching was considered.
- Mover/Leavers: We were not as interested to see where they went to, but we are interested rather to collect their narrative about the reasons why they left/moved, or what their experience was of the Garcia university/institutional period. Here there are several similarities, such as feeling of disgust at a competitive culture and lack of collaborative culture. Women leavers have a sense of regret of not "having achieved or being able to continue" in the academic/scientific sector. There is in all cases, lack of support often voiced and paired with regret. Also the experience of constant accountability, hyper productivity for women and men, but even more so for women, as it tends of infringe upon family life. There are some common disciplinary differences, as STEM leavers speak about lack of PhD recognition in terms of status and salary, especially in engineering.
- Almost without exception, parenthood tips the scale of interviewees' ambivalence, with females experiencing more ambivalence; in some cases, you see fewer parents or even motherhood renounced.
- For newly tenured, the double-edged flexibility of research work is something many interviewees speak about; the difficulty of keeping work and family life separate. Women have more trouble prioritizing work over family life and chores; female carer (and modified breadwinner) models are still present in most countries (Belgium, Iceland, Switzerland, Italy childlessness compatible with career, in Iceland also in STEM, in Belgium also more in STEM childless): the regret and guilt as an important difference between the work/life balance experience of female and male newly tenured. This regardless of STEM or SSH; however, more males voice this also in SSH.
- Mobility is a crucial factor for career success and advancement, whereby there is less mobility possible for women, especially where motherhood is concerned, depending on flexibility of partner and also funds abroad and host country. Males speak more positively of mobility experience, but explain how spouses or partners have been very flexible or also sacrificing their own stability of potential or real careers.
- For movers, mobility has become a must in order to survive within the career pathway; often with some important sacrifices and difficulties in terms of private and family life conciliation (long travelling or commuting hours, partners having to give up etc.).
- Networks and mentors are considered essential for recruitment and professional advancement in all countries. Especially those having experienced a positive support and networking possibilities speak about its utmost importance for their own career advancement and what is considered success in obtaining permanent positions and having been integrated into the centres or research groups. However, women in SSH are lonelier, and male in STEM are more lonely heroes; SSH males are most collaborative and have most "cooptation" possibilities.
- The possibility of continuing the academic career was also entwined with fundraising capacity.
- Confidence: there is some difference in the way women and men speak about moving and the feelings attached to it: there is more confidence and positive life choices voiced by male interviewees' leavers, rather than for females, who express regret, also lack of confidence.

- Most interviewees, especially postdocs, are not too critical about work demands and conditions: they often considered this “normal” in order to follow this career path (see Belgium, especially STEM, and Switzerland, especially women, fitting into the masculine habitus): non-questioning of demands, although considered heavy and full of difficulties.

Recruitment and discursive resources

A clear transversal feature is that scientific “excellence” or competition-based criteria (numbers of articles, obtaining research grants, types of journals...) matter in the primary stage of selection in application procedures for permanent positions. Then in a second round, more nomination and local or “subjective” criteria will play a major role and make the difference in the achievement of nomination; this nomination plays everywhere. However, in all country cases, there is a clear tension between the discursive resources for early researchers (women and men), which are more the productivity-based competition-based criteria for career access, and the discursive resources of committee members that are more orientated towards nomination-based, local and “subjective” criteria, after an overall estimation of “excellence” in a candidate, which is also productivity-based as a prerequisite. In all country cases there is a clear gap between formal and informal recruitment criteria, and a lack of transparency about the latter.

Finally, the discourse of “excellence” appears to take on quite negative connotations in both the SSH and STEM faculties. More precisely, it is a critical evaluation of the criteria on which excellence could or should be judged that is shared by recruitment committee members. This enables them to justify the introduction of “subjective” selection criteria into the early-career selection procedures and to reject the sole use of bibliometric or financial performance measures. These indicators are not presented as unimportant. In practice, they are often used to reach a “short list” of prospective candidates and are presented as perfectly legitimate tools at this stage of the selection process. It is after this first “sifting” exercise that they become redundant and that more “qualitative” indicators are sought.” Institutional knowledge of codes and local cultures is considered very important in all country cases, and that this can be got by through important gatekeepers and mentors, to which in all country cases early researchers that are women have less access, and less assistance.

Organizational features/modalities

A clear common feature is that funding plays a major role in shaping careers: in SSH there is less funding for research and teaching, and there is less per student funding. Women, who are more present in SSH are therefore less funded overall. In STEM they are less present, whereby there is more funding for STEM, for PhDs, as well as per student. In SSH moreover, there is more per student/teacher ratio. There is in all country cases a constant bid for funding experienced on all early career levels (docs, postdocs, newly tenured). This constant bid takes up a lot of their time, which they would otherwise have used to do actual research. This presents an extra hurdle in terms of overwork and omnipresence for women. Women have a harder time obtaining funding, whether they be postdocs or academics. The reason for this is that there is in funding systems and applications a clear focus upon hyper-productivist criteria (publications, mobility, international and local network membership), which puts women at a disadvantage. Funding also depends highly on the supervisor (PhD and Postdoc); having a supportive supervisor, who him-or herself belongs to strong networks can facilitate stronger applications. In general women have lesser supportive supervisors and lesser strategic guidance, and have more trouble gaining access to international (due to lack or difficulty of mobility) and local networks (due to lack of difficulty of embeddedness and mentoring).

There is generally, in all country cases less assistance for teaching, whereby there are more women teaching assistants. Teaching is in most country cases a task that is undervalued, despite being one of the pillars of academic work, and despite becoming an important criterion for nomination for tenured positions. There is generally a gap between research based doctoral and postdoctoral criteria orientations, and then including teaching as a criterion upon nomination.

There is a lot of administrative workload upon early researchers and academics, which adds to overwork and shifting balance of work away from other, more valued and necessary tasks (research). In most country cases, the administrative and technical staff is predominantly female.

There is in most country cases an important glass ceiling in terms of the presence of women in management and leadership positions, and in recruitment and promotion committees.

4. THREE TYPES OF GENDERED PIPELINES

After the transversal diagnosis, we present three types of “**career paths and organizations**” that show different configurations, characteristics and composition trends for the different elements that are recurring in the six country case study vignettes. What we could analyse is that despite the similarities comparing the six country cases, we can observe significant differences on the levels of contexts, of gender policy development, of a culture of work and career organization, of work / family interference. These dimensions far from being autonomous in each case, are in a relationship of interstructuralization. Thus by comparing the six cases/vignettes, it is clear that the case studies are in a relationship of **distance or proximity between the different dimensions**. By analyzing these distances and proximities between the six cases, we can then identify different logical structuring of pipelines. Thus, three more distinctive logics have been identified as types of gendered pipelines, namely:

- Type (1) “Persisting in precariousness” career path and “Mandarin” organisation with High cumulative costs;
- Type (2) “Persisting in uncertainty and ambivalence” career path and “University institution” organizational model with Moderate level costs;
- Type (3) “Winning in competition” career path and “market-driven” organization with Specific Costs.

If the Type (1) has been mainly deduced from the Italian and Slovenian cases, the Type (2) from the Belgian and Icelandic cases, and the Type (3) from the Netherlands and Swiss cases, this typology is not a classification of countries and institutions, but more a typology of rationales (meta). These three types of gendered pipelines show different configurations of costs for three entity levels (macro/meso/micro), which are presented in a table given below. However, caution needs to be exercised when interpreting the level of costs: we cannot simply add up numbers of costs for each entity and classify the types on a scale of more or less costs: we need to consider the type of costs that can incur on each level, and the range of costs. Is the particular type of gendered pipeline generating many different types of costs? For example, The Type (1) has a large variety of individual costs, such as professional development, job security and institutional membership, personal well-being (health, work/life balance, sense of satisfaction), flexibility in careers. It also gathers simultaneously a wide range of meso-level and macro-level costs. From this range of costs on all three levels, we can speak about a gendered pipeline with **high-level cumulative costs**. The other two gendered pipeline types (2) and (3) gather more **moderate and more specific level costs**. However, the complexity (density and interplay) of the different aspects composing the gendered pipeline also means we need to exercise caution in classifying types, especially as other costs that are not gleaned from the results may exist, and are not listed. Rather than classifying the types, we can consider this table as a way of better understanding the (A) interplay between the different entities, namely the “**Cost Rationale**” (B) how this matters to gender dynamics and inequalities, in short the “**Gendered Impacts**”. These two analytical dimensions are included in each Type.

TYPE 1: “Persisting in precariousness” career path and “Mandarin” organisation with High cumulative costs

Gender and Welfare regimes

This type of leaky pipeline is characterized by traditional gender roles in society, therefore traditional male breadwinner and female carer roles in gender regimes. Moreover, in line with this traditional role distribution, few or no effective childcare and elderly support systems exist within society. This is replicated within the university system itself. On the labour market, we find that the economic participation rate of women is still considerably lower than that of men. Women’s access to the labour market, remuneration, career advancement, promotion to positions of leadership and new business initiatives remains relatively low. Young women are more likely than young men to be unemployed, and to be employed in less stable forms of employment and in the lowest-paid sectors (horizontal segregation). This is replicated also in the academic sector, with an important sticky floor in terms of assistant teaching non-tenured positions (and technical and administrative staff) with a majority of women. There remains an important gender pay gap, which exists also in the academic

sector. The structural situation of young researchers is characterized by low level of salaries, lack of social protection, few opportunities on the labour market, etc. However, higher education is becoming increasingly feminised, whereby gender stereotypes persist in fields.

Gender Policy

There is no real active gender and equality policy, neither on the national level, nor on the institutional level in academia.

Work culture and organization

There is a strictly linear academic path, with few positions and stringent competition, with an emphasis on productivist recruitment criteria (numerous publications in “high-level” peer reviewed international journals, indicators especially in STEM). There is a high-level uncertainty for postdoctoral researchers and there are numerous short-term, non-permanent research and teaching contracts and employee body. In this non-permanent “floating” body, postdocs are not recognized as official employees with social and same financial benefits.

This institution is engaged discursively in internationalization and economic measures and standards. International mobility is highlighted, however the institution remains relatively closed in terms of local recruitment for postdoctoral contracts, and for permanent positions. There is lesser funding overall for research by governments, and this institution tries to encourage international funding.

In this type there is a vast power of full professors well established, which tend to be more male figures. Moreover, we can observe that these male mentors are powerful gatekeepers to networks that allow a succession to male junior colleagues, a feature which is lacking for their female peers. This points to a mandarin type organization.

Work/life interference

Early researchers and academics, particularly women, experiment a work/family conflict. Often, maternity and academic career are considered and lived as incompatible in the kinds of demands and conditions of research/academic careers; especially in terms of job precariousness and hyper-productivity as a clear requirement for CV building. In this type, women sacrifice motherhood in order to persist or survive in the career.

Cost rationale

This Type combines a large range and high level of costs in different levels (see Table). The individual level is characterized by a very high level of professional insecurity, non-integration and non-stabilization on the level of the institution. Institutional membership is not given for the early career researchers in this organization, and it brings with it several repercussions on the level of the institution as well as for the larger Scientific community. The numerous short-term contracts employs quite a large “floating” and non-stabilized worker body, dedicated to fundamental research. However the institution structures fundamental research in a short-term and non-continued way. As individuals are moreover self-responsible, with lesser assistance in terms of supervisors and colleagues, fundamental research remains a rather haphazard concern, at the mercy of funding opportunities and availabilities. Moreover, a significant feature of this type is the high level of costs in terms of teaching: teaching is not favoured by individual early career researchers, however there are an increasing number of non-stabilized assistants, who assume teaching tasks, which are however barely recognized, especially in terms of criteria for permanent positions, which is largely focused upon publications and research development. Teaching therefore is assumed by a large non-stabilized undervalued workers’ body, which undervalues this task for these very reasons. Arguably, this is not very favourable for teaching itself, that remains a secondary task compared to research that is over-valued due to recruitment criteria and to the form of the PhD and the postdoctoral projects and short-term contracts. It is moreover classified as a sticky floor, which is not favourable for the Scientific level nor for the institutional level.

There remains in this type a very thick glass ceiling and slow career progression for women, which is coupled with masculine cooptation logics and non-existing support in terms of supervision and networks for women. In parallel, in this type there is a work/family conflict, penalizing workers with families, as the linearity, high demands and non-flexibility of working conditions and careers, and hyper-productivity as a recruitment criteria and institutional omnipresence do not allow for an easy and even possible work/private life conciliation. This organization moreover does not take into account the lack of childcare and family services in society and does not provide any services on its

own account. On the whole, women who are mothers or who wish to be mothers have a particular hard time, and often renounce parenthood due to impossible career conciliation. Career and professional assistance and development is moreover not given. The Scientific and institutional community has to ask itself questions about what kind of worker profile it wants to promote, which currently is rather homogeneous, linear and mono-profile, orientated towards an outdated masculine omnipresent profile, and whether Science itself would stagnate in its persistence of the types of researchers/academics it is represented by. The questions for the missions of the institution and Scientific community and output are intimately linked with its workers position, conditions and membership, and the way work is operating and operated. Here we find a particularly greedy institution, which however does not offer membership to a large floating body of workers, working on fundamental research development and teaching.

Gendered impacts

Women early researchers and academics have a high level and wide range of costs; they have a particularly hard time getting stabilized, as there is an accumulation of short-term contracts, and if they are on permanent posts, it is more on assistantship teaching levels. Teaching however is considered less gratifying, so this presents a sticky floor to them, preventing them from doing research. However, the kind of research focus that they are required to do, is for building the CV, they are focussed on productivity criteria (publications) as a discursive resource. Moreover, in this type of institution, there is a high level of importance of guidance from mentors, especially on the strategic level, and for access to networks that seem very significant for accessing career opportunities. Informal recruitment criteria moreover are not very visible and the processes themselves are non-transparent, especially for women who lack mentors to give them respective advice/institutional knowledge. Women lack both of these assistances; few to no mentors, and a lack of belonging to networks that matter. They also experience precariousness on the personal and wellbeing level, as burnouts and anxiety are frequent due to the insecurity and instability of their job situations. In stable positions, they also experience overwork. If they do not have assistantship positions, they experience a lack of social schemes and lack of institutional embeddedness (membership). They also have a harder time to balance work and personal or family life. This causes often sacrifices on the level of motherhood; preferring to deter or renounce motherhood due to gaining access to career and progression. This is reinforced by a general lack of childcare and elderly services in society, where traditional gender roles are still in place. In terms of opportunities to convert the PhD and the career into other sectors, especially the SSH women loose out too, because the PhD is not easily recognized in other sectors. In STEM this is somewhat easier. So even the avenue of professional reconversion is arduous and not that wide. We can look at a very *precarious overall situation, and high degree of gender inequality for early career women researchers/academics*, compared to their male peers, although early career males also have generally a hard time to acquire permanent positions. However, they are more equipped for gaining access and for promotion purposes, and they sacrifice less on a personal level.

TYPE 2: “Persisting in uncertainty and ambivalence” career path and “University institution” organizational model with Moderate level costs

Gender and Welfare regimes

In this type we are looking at traditional to mixed welfare state and gender regimes, with a prevalent of the dual-breadwinner/female carer model. This economic system has achieved much in terms of feminine employment. There can occur a part-time feature of female employment, also implying a hidden one-and-a-half breadwinner model (male full-time/female part-time work in couple). There persists also an unexplained moderate gender gap. The social security system is universally protective (good social benefits) and the conditions of employment are well regulated (minimum wage, job protection...), with replication in academia. There are also in this social system a quite developed childcare service and family leave measures (short and flexible parental leave for instance). However, the organization of work remains non family-friendly for academia, with overwork, hyper-productivity and productivist recruitment criteria.

Gender stereotypes persist despite a pronounced feminization of higher education: STEM remains still predominately male. There is a bottleneck after PhD and during or after Postdoc, with few permanent positions and a high competition. There are persisting glass ceilings, especially for leadership and management positions.

Gender policy

There is a lot of discourse about gender and equality policy and laws, which exist on national level, also sometimes on the levels of research institutions, without however so far concrete implementation plans. There is some institutional resistance to implementing gender policy and measures; notably an ambiguous discourse about gender and recruitment processes, or about quotas on recruitment committees and in leadership, or on any existence of gender bias, in STEM mostly.

Work/life interference

Early researchers, both men and women, speak about work life imbalance and parental ambivalence. SSH early researchers and newly tenured academics are more often parents, whereas STEM doctorates and postdocs are childless, and sometimes continue being even at more settled positions.

Especially women leavers speak about how continuing would also mean sacrificing work/family balance. Male leavers also spoke about not wanting to go down this road, however they speak about their “leaving” with more distance, and more of a personal choice toward a better present or future, whereas women leavers remain somewhat ambiguous and have regrets. Women early researchers/academics in this type are more fraught with guilt than their male counterparts, about juggling working life and family life. There is however, overall in this type, a clear parental ambivalence (not entirely comfortable with work/family balance, harder time for parents), for both women (more) and men.

Work culture and Organization

There exist co-optation logics, which are maintained by mostly male gatekeepers and “following” a mentor is more possible for men, which points to mobilizing masculinities. There are less female “role models” and less support from gatekeepers for women.

Early stage researchers (those currently still working and those having left the institution), but also newly tenured speak about a productivist and competition culture, with less collaboration culture. Especially horizontal collaboration or collaboration with senior academics (mostly male) is considered very hard to come by, and often newly tenured academics collaborate more with junior colleagues (docs, postdocs in their own teams). Women newly tenured have a harder time finding senior colleagues to collaborate with, especially in STEM; they also have a harder time composing own research teams and having access to funding. In SSH, both men and women have a hard time composing their own research teams.

A constant bid for funding characterizes this type; individual early researchers, early academics and research centres, as well as the whole research institutions are bidding for governmental and international funding. This governmental bid is sustained by a “point-system” (awarding centres or individuals by amount of research produced or funding obtained externally) or a “closed envelope system” (universities receive funding according to number of students but with a constant global amount divided between universities): these systems in this type reinforce a competition culture, for units and amongst individuals. A lot of time is spent during work for writing funding applications. There is a clear gender budgeting issue with these systems, as there is more per student funding for STEM than for SSH. At the same time, there is in SSH a higher pro student-teacher ratio: STEM is male dominated, so women in SSH lose out on funding possibilities, and in STEM are in a minority, thus also having less access to funding. This funding issue persists for PhD in both fields. Academics have to bid in order to have PhDs; women academics have a harder time obtaining funding, and women researchers have a harder time obtaining funding (in both SSH and STEM).

There is an institutional emphasis on internationalization, excellence (high research production and funding) and competition discourse. However, this is often in tension with a highly locally developed organizational and (negotiation) “culture” or local ways of doing things.

This institution often can be classified as professional bureaucracy with lesser support for teaching and research units and more for central governance (commissions/committees). They are

characterized by a high level of auto-management of each unit or individual academic/researcher. This administrative work takes up a lot of time. Some early career researchers that are women complain of a sticky floor linked to doing non-prestigious administrative tasks.

In this type, early career researchers, both men and women, but more women, complain about omnipresence (having to do everything and be everywhere, in all meetings at the same time) and overwork. They speak about a double edged flexibility that characterizes their work; they love doing research, less so teaching, but they feel that this passion-type work, and the flexibility of being to work anytime and anywhere can infringe upon private and family life, and they have trouble “switching the off button”. They also are often lonely heroes and heroines, especially for a long time in STEM, however finding this “normal”. This type characterizes itself with many early researchers and newly tenured taking the work conditions and nature of work, and personal sacrifices “in their stride”; this is normal for this kind of career.

PhD reconversion into other sectors is not easy for SSH in terms of value, salary, job satisfaction and opportunities. In STEM this is easier, especially for male leavers. However, not on the level of salaries: Engineers are not paid more due to PhD. So PhD often not recognized on salary scale in STEM.

In recruitment processes and structures in this institution, there are tensions between formal/informal selection criteria – also between competition-based (publications, mobility) and nomination-based criteria (finding the ideal candidate who “fits” and who will be a future colleague). The former competition-based criteria are major discursive resources for early career researchers, whereas the latter tend to be discursive resources for recruitment committee members. These latter nomination-based criteria are however less transparent and are more likely to be taken into consideration in applications if applicants have local institutional knowledge of organizational codes and cultures, and are integrated in networks. International mobility, in this type, is a significant asset for gaining permanent positions: early researchers try as much as possible to do doctorates or postdocs abroad, as this is seen as a clear requirement criterion for applications. This mobility is more difficult for women, especially mothers. On the whole, this type characterises a precarious and ambivalent balance achieved, or not achieved, for women and men in early career stages, depending to a high level on their respective partners. Male early researchers and academics often have partners with part-time or no work, and who take the primary carer role in their family. Women in early career stages have cooperative partners, who assume carer roles alongside them, or else they don’t, and these women have a harder time, and are practically non-existent, especially in the newly tenured sample.

Cost Rationale

In this Type the moderate costs are to be found in all especially the macro level of Science, but which carry some weight in terms of university missions and pillars. The institutional context moreover is based on some financially constraining frameworks that reinforce certain trends. The massification of students is reinforced by a governmental funding system(s) that create competition between universities and research institutions in order to “bid” for funding. Student numbers are deemed indicators for more or less funding allocation. However, there is also lesser teaching staff and lesser academic positions for PhDs/postdocs to come by, and the conversion value of the PhD in certain fields such as SSH is low. So there are more PhDs/postdocs in short-term contracts developing fundamental research and teaching, but also a lesser continuity in the careers and in professional development and contribution to university environment. Professional development is a point that remains obsolete in terms of value of PhD: what is the possibility of the PhDs offered at university and research institutions beyond academia? Why does the institution engage many PhDs and postdocs, possibly for funding reasons and development of fundamental research and cheap teaching staff, but what is the continuity in terms of profession?

Also, there is a disproportionate funding system for STEM and SSH (and other) fields. STEM has more funding, but lesser women. SSH has lesser funding and more women present. So in each field women struggle more, as they have to compete with more male colleagues for funding in STEM, and in SSH get lesser funding for their research, and thus more competition too. The Gender stereotypes in fields are thus reinforced. Generally, the organizational system(s) in this type point to a reinforcing of a competition rather than collaboration culture. Workers (researchers/academics) have a hard time to integrate into and create their research teams, especially early career women. In conjuncture to this, the organizational system reinforces a system of auto-management of units, with an administrative system that supports the central governance, rather than research and

teaching units, and individuals. Fulfilling all the different missions and tasks becomes arduous for workers and units, and has a high level of self-reliance, which university assistance is rare to come by, and collaboration between colleagues is more difficult. Workers are struggling to keep up the work load, the omnipresence and the strain of self-management, and getting help where it is given (mentors, supervisors, colleagues); women loose out on these matters.

The university and research institution can ask itself if this kind of culture and organizational system is likely to create a worker-friendly environment, or a more collaborative and community-based culture. The Scientific community moreover emphasises that Science is a majorly collaborative work, and recruitment criteria for committees are equally focussing on the importance of local integration and capacity to collaborate; the institution needs to ask itself whether this criteria requirement is justified in this particular institutional environment, and whether the system itself also needs to offer the structures to be able to integrate and collaborate.

Gendered Impacts

Early career researchers and academics, both women and men in this case, have to maintain a precarious balance in order to gain access to the career, and then to progress in the career. However, this *balancing is more difficult to achieve for women compared to their male counterparts*. In this type of institution and system too, there is the importance of gatekeepers, mentors and belonging to the right kind of networks, whether they be international or local institutional networks; women have less access to networks and have less advice from their supervisors, who are often a far cry from mentors. SSH men have more access to mentors within the institutional framework, whereas STEM males rely less on mentors and are more of solo players. STEM and SSH postdoc and newly tenured women have more internationally based mentors. However, this presupposes having international networks.

The kind of recruitment criteria that are highlighted are two-fold as well, and present a kind of rock and the hard place for women; productivity-based criteria, such as publications in the right kind of journals and in STEM also numbers and indicator-based. Here, mobility also is a criterion for “excellence” in a CV or application file: early researchers try as much as possible to do PhDs, but mostly postdocs abroad. Or else, they are coming from neighbouring countries and can demonstrate mobility. Then there is the high institutional significance in this type of local institutional knowledge of codes, of what is expected from committee members and “locals” about how to “fit in”; this knowledge can be again, as in Type (1), gained by belonging to local networks, be guided by mentors, which women have a lack of compared to their male peers.

Women have a harder time achieving both types of criteria, as it can interfere with family life, or motherhood that is frequent in SSH for postdoc women, and newly tenured. STEM women postdocs tend not to have children yet, and wait to be newly tenured to have children, which sometimes take a longer time than in SSH. Again, the balance towards gaining a permanent position can be achieved if all the configurations are “right”; if you have a supportive supervisor, if you have a supportive private partner in life, who takes over part of the care and household responsibilities, if you can work overtime and invest sufficiently in achieving productivity and in being omnipresent (research production, funding, teaching, institutional engagement, administrative tasks). However, the chances that all these configurations are present simultaneously are quite low for women. They are easier for men to achieve. Professional reconversion is not something easy for women, as they have more regrets about leaving academia and have a lingering sense of failure, despite having other jobs in other sectors, whereas men voice more of a personal distance to academia, and voice more satisfaction. In STEM moreover, the PhD status is often not recognized, in terms of status and salary level; engineers earn level of masters despite having a PhD. So the value of PhD remains somewhat ambiguous.

This Type has a high level of ambiguity for women also on the level of parenthood; upon becoming mothers, they have a harder time to be hyper-productive and omnipresent, and experience more guilt about work and family, doing either. Male parents also are ambiguous, but they have more support otherwise; partners assuming main care and household chores, and flexibility in terms of mobility for example; they have more mentors and institutional assistance from networks, they revel in the flexibility that the type of research work offers and do not feel guilty about work/family. So *more ambiguity and a harder to achieve precarious balance, with the need of the “right” configurations*, characterizes this type in terms of gender inequality for women, compared to their male peers.

TYPE 3: “Winning in competition” career path and “market-driven” organization with Specific Costs

Gender and Welfare Regimes

This type is characterised by modified male breadwinner gender regimes or “one-and-a-half earner models”, where female part-time character of work is frequent in overall labour market. Striking difference to the part-time national trend is to be found in academia, where full-time employment of women is to be found. Childcare services are available, but very expensive and exclusive (few numbers of children per service, few services). Compared to men, women are still primarily responsible for and spend more time on childcare and domestic work. Despite a culture of taking care of children in the family (by the mother), the use of formal childcare has increased rapidly. In terms of statistics, ongoing PhDs are only one-third women compared to their male peers. Gender stereotypes persist in favour of males in STEM. There is a glass ceiling the higher we climb, especially ordinary professorships and management positions. There are still few women in leadership positions, although marginally present in all levels and posts. There is a particularly thin bottleneck, with very few permanent positions and few chances of becoming stabilized. However, there is also a highly buoyant extra-academic labour market, which is availed by PhD holders, also in SSH.

Gender Policy

There is a strong national gender policy discourse and softer governance is opted for through quota introductions, rather than through structural and cultural changes. There is some gender policy also in academic institutions, although it is mostly an overall diversity policy in HR. There are elaborate mentoring programmes already in place, with peer mentoring and promotion of women in science, wide-ranging and relatively well-funded equal opportunity measures available, especially at the doctoral level. This is less the case for the postdoctoral level, which remains still institutionally invisible in terms of an employee body. However, these measures are geared toward “coaching champions”, or selecting the most “excellent” or best researchers. Competition for these funding possibilities is all the more competitive. The programmes are however not yet evaluated for their success rates for women in long term for careers.

Work/life interference

There are yet lesser children for women in academia and a clear parental ambivalence for women and lesser so for men. There are however big differences between STEM and SSH in terms of parenthood, with STEM being often childless.

Work culture and Organization

In this type, early career researchers and academics speak about the notion of ‘self-driven’ work, a problem of work taking over everything: double-edged flexibility and passion. Moreover, they speak about juggling with different tasks once they are tenured, which is experienced as being problematic and infringing upon work/family and private life balance.

In terms of teaching, there seems more pressures in STEM to teach for career progression, thus making of teaching a criterion, and more real inclination was voiced toward teaching in SSH.

Early researchers and academics have a “taking it into stride” attitude, both men and women, whereby especially women speak about making sacrifices, instability and overwork. There is a clear tension and ambivalence voiced by women about work and care. Early researchers/academic women mirror the societal persisting majorly caring role of women. Moreover, the intensity of the tension around work-life balance strongly depends on gender- role arrangement with the partner.

There emerges in this type, an idea of the idealised “all-round” academic profile, which is thought to be well suited to an increasingly international and competitive environment. This ideal-type figure is expected to “perform” equally well in research (by attracting competitive external funding - notably to keep the post-docs in employment -, and publishing in the top international, peer-reviewed journals), in teaching (by attracting high quality graduate students), and in maintaining high levels of “organisational wellbeing” (particularly by taking on administrative duties). In addition, this (imaginary) figure of academic equilibrium should know how to non-academic activities (leisure, sport, culture, even family-life...).

This type characterises itself as hosting an important international flux of students compared to other countries and institutions. There are many postdoc contracts on international or external funding, not necessarily however leading to tenure-track or permanent academic positions. The locally funded career pathways are still more favourable compared to incoming international postdocs when it comes to obtaining permanent positions. Despite being embedded in the international market, the university is not seen as attractive for employment for locals, despite being regionally strongly embeddedness. There is an increasing number of short-term contracts and non-tenured assistant professor positions. This is not the case for associate and full professors; we are looking at a glass ceiling already at associateship level. There are many lonely heroes and heroines, with numerous boys' clubs, and some more recent girls' clubs; some women mentors promoting women.

Early researchers and newly tenured academics speak about a constant bid for funding for research and for advancement of networks and strategic guidance, which is considered as very key in career advancement. Postdocs tend to focus upon research and CV building, whereas teaching is seen as a necessity or obligation for tenureship, or when already tenured also for promotion toward professorship. In terms of criteria for recruitment, and in promotion, in STEM, the passage of acquiring grants is considered a must.

Movers from this institution speak about having had a supportive network and mentors, preferring this flexibility of work, the type of work that they like, having precarious balance depending on family support. Leavers however point out that they did not experience real embeddedness in the institution.

The selection processes are governed with formal criteria due to gender equality policy, however these formalized criteria focus on initial quantifiable research, then "subjective" factors that are non-transparent, such as the "all-round" or "ideal-type" academic. In this type, quota or excellence-based equality measures reinforce competition, and may reinforce a market-driven logic of academic recruitment.

Cost Rationale

In this type of career path and organization, specific costs are incurred on all three levels, whereby the Scientific community suffers too in terms of the persistence of gender stereotypes in fields (STEM/SSH), in terms of fundamental research here too is governed by funding competition, and remains haphazard. The specificity of this type lies also in a very stringent and steep and slow career progression in a very elite organization. Jobs are very hard to come by and rare: hard to come by because they require a profile of an 'all-round' ideal academic who is capable of self-administration, institutional embeddedness and omnipresence (being present in all tasks, research, teaching, service to institution, society), but also rare because positions are scarce. PhD conversion is somewhat better in this type in the non-academic sectors, there is more collaboration for PhD conversion. However, the career is made possible when a whole set of conditions are met; when you have supportive mentors, when you are in the right networks, when you have a supportive partner working half-time and assuming the primary care role. There is some institutional support required in pre-existing gender policy and programs, but which are still very elitist, exclusive and "excellence" based, focused on the requirements of hyper-productivity, publication lists in international peer reviewed journals and existence and membership of internal and external networks.

Gendered Impacts

Women early researchers and academics have a ***harder time juggling with many things at the same time than their male counterparts***; like in the Type (2), there is a hard to achieve balance between work and family life, with overwork and omnipresence. However, there is less ambiguity on the individual level, except upon parenthood. There are however, even less job opportunities in this type, because there are few positions and very less chances to attain them. The extra-academic labour market however seems to be buoyant, but the recognition of the PhD in other sectors is possibly less transparent for early researchers. Although there are developed institutional mentoring programmes and financial measures to assist women in science, these have pronounced productivity criteria, reinforcing competition and reinforcing hyper-productivity: women have still a hard time achieving this, due to a lack of assistance, due to persisting traditional gender roles and assuming main care roles. A self-driven and self-imposed masculine habitus, of being totally engaged, and of a double edged flexibility that allows for work all the time and everywhere creates

work/life imbalance reigns in this Type, especially for women, as it tends to infringe upon family life. For their male counterparts, they often have partners who work part-time, and who assume main carer roles. For newly tenured females, they maintain, as the Type (2), a precarious balance, depending on the presence of a supportive partner and of supportive private network (parents looking after children etc.), as child care services are very expensive and hard to get by, and of an institutional supportive network accessed by important gatekeepers/mentors. However, this is a very rare configuration for women, as there are powerful cooptation logics and old boys' clubs. And the overall balance is very hard to maintain the higher you climb in the career, as overwork and omnipresence (research production, bid for funding), teaching, institutional engagement, administrative tasks) become more pronounced the higher the positions (professorship and management). In terms of gender inequality, in this Type (3), **women have a hard time winning or accessing a stringent competition-based system, elitist institution and career, and then maintaining this highly demanding position**, compared to their male peers, who have more set configurations for a long-term period.

Table of costs

Three levels of entities/ Costs	Type 1: “Persisting in precariousness” career path and mandarin organisation with <i>High Cumulative Costs</i>	Type 2: “Persisting in uncertainty and ambivalence” career path and “University institution” organisation with <i>Moderate Costs</i>	Type 3: “Winning in competition” career path and “market-driven” organisation with <i>Specific Costs</i>
<p>Macro level entity: science</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Important scientific exchanges and development between teaching and research may suffer, as teaching is undervalued both on meso- and micro-levels. - Increased short-term knowledge production contracts, with lesser funding of fundamental research. - Less depth of research undertaken: short-term contracts, with more deadlines and hyper-productivity in terms of publications: The temporariness of research affects the quality of research outputs and the type of knowledge elaborated in academia. - Lesser diversity in research and teaching in terms of gender, fewer female role models, persistence of masculine-based scientific research work model - Brain-drain for academia and other sectors: feminised higher education, but little career chances in academia and conversion of PhD in SSH - Decreasing the purpose and value of the PhD.: accepting many doctorates, but with what aim. - Scientific organisations contributing to a work/family contradiction. - Persisting gender stereotypes in SSH and STEM fields. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Persisting gender stereotypes for STEM: few women/fewer men in SSH - Student attraction for funding reasons: less teacher/student ratio, despite rising number of students: more degrees, with lesser quality of teaching programmes. - Lesser governmental funding, especially in SSH - Scientific production governed by funding structures: lesser fundamental research, lesser SSH research - Gender stereotypes persist in favour of males in STEM. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Scientific production governed by funding measures: competitive criteria - Research and Teaching continue to be produced by an elite, more homogenous group of researchers/academics - Gender stereotypes persist in favour of males in STEM.

<p>Meso level entity: institution</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Large number of non-stabilized, “floating” not fully integrated research body and assistantship teaching staff - Teaching remaining undervalued: non-academic assistantship staff assuming main load of teaching, whereby teaching is not a main concern or passion; seen often as necessity for career progression - Slower career climb and high vertical glass-ceiling for women in leadership and management for both teaching and research - Co-optation logics, old boys’ clubs, high importance of gatekeepers and “following” a mentor more possible for men, less female “role models” and less support from gatekeepers for women. - No effective childcare and elderly support system in society at large, and at institutional level not taken into consideration - Institutional ambivalence and discrepancy of and during recruitment procedures - Linear, non-flexible career paths for researchers/academics - Value of PhD other than in academia for SSH questionable - Value of PhD in terms of salary and status in other sectors not guaranteed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Funding systems: closed envelope/point systems: Universities, research and teaching units, bid for funding according to student numbers: competition and student attraction - Per student rata for STEM 3 times higher than for SSH, however more SSH students. - More funding for STEM PhDs, and less for SSH: more male PhDs in STEM, and less so in SSH, so double disadvantages, and reinforcing gendered budgeting - Co-optation logics, old boys’ clubs, high importance of gatekeepers and “following” a mentor more possible for men, less female “role models” and less support from gatekeepers for women. - Tensions between internationalization/standards in “excellence”, and local institutional criteria, codes, embeddedness, power of local culture, of committees, and networks - Lesser funding for researchers/academics: bidding and competition culture on institution, institute and individual level reinforced. Funding harder to obtain for women academics, and researchers. - Competition rather than collaboration amongst and academics and within/between research groups - Non transparent recruitment processes: attracting the “wrong” type of researchers/future academics: lonely heroes/lonely heroines, non-integrated, focused upon research rather than also teaching, due to focus and discursive resources of recruitment criteria of competition - Recruitment committees haphazard in terms of gender policy, especially in STEM: gap between formal and informal criteria - Value of PhD in terms of salary and status in other sectors not guaranteed (STEM engineering for example) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Less attractiveness of academia within the job market. - Very narrow bottleneck after PhD and postdoc. Very few positions and few chances of obtaining permanent positions - Side effects of existing gender equality measures: recruiting “excellence” that is still based on hyper-productivity and omnipresence (being constantly available) based criteria (high level and number of publications in renowned journals, mobility); reinforcing competitiveness. - Policy orientated toward internationalization: tensions with local recruitment, local culture and institutional codes - Gender stereotypes persist in favour of males in STEM. - There is a vertical glass ceiling the higher we climb, especially ordinary professorships and management positions. - Local over international funding in favour of tenure-track: importance of local embeddedness and - an overall institutional (all-round academic) implication, that is less often the case for women
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<p>Three levels of entities/ Costs</p>	<p>Type 1: “Persisting in precariousness” career path and mandarin organisation with <i>High Cumulative Costs</i></p>	<p>Type 2: “Persisting in uncertainty and ambivalence” career path and “University institution” organisation with <i>Moderate Costs</i></p>	<p>Type 3: “Winning in competition” career path and “market-driven” organisation with <i>Specifics Costs</i></p>
<p>Micro level entity: individual researcher /academic</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dissatisfaction - Career instability, precariousness and uncertainty - Lack of professional development - Postdocs not as official employees, lesser social scheme and institutional benefits - High dependence on existing networks and mentors: women have lack of both - Lack of PHD conversion towards other sectors, mainly for SSH - Lack of institutional recognition and full membership - Slower career progression for women, glass ceilings - Lack of collaboration - Lack of guidance, strategic for career building - Lack of guidance, for professional (research and teaching) development - Burnouts - Work/life imbalance - Parental ambivalence - Renouncing parenthood, for women mainly - No effective childcare and elderly support system in society 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Career instability and uncertainty - Parental ambiguity - High dependence on existing network, existing mentors: women have lack of both - High dependence on supportive private network, especially partners (for men, part-time work of partner, for women, partner assuming care too, but mostly also in full-time); availability and assuming of care, of mobility - Ambiguity on level of work/life balance - more for women: guilt expressed in women about time away from work, and time away from children. - Omnipresence, overwork, hyper productivity, CV “bodybuilding” for career - PHD conversion not easy for SSH (value, salary, status, job satisfaction, opportunities) - Leavers women: lack of distance, regrets about not “having succeeded” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Very narrow bottleneck after PhD and postdoc, very few positions and few chances of obtaining permanent position. - Omnipresence, overwork, hyper productivity as source of stress, anxiety and ambiguity, in terms of work/life balance and health - Precarious balance of keeping the winning position, or of being able to juggle tasks, hyper productivity and criteria for recruitment and progression. - ‘Self-driven’ work and double edged flexibility: not being able to separate work and private life due to the nature of work, and also the passion for work, being able to do it everywhere and anytime. Especially infringing upon family life for women. - High dependence on supportive private network, especially partners, who are available for care. - Not enough support for postdocs, especially women, as gender equality measures and mentoring programmes are more geared toward ongoing PhDs.

5. CONCLUSION AND PERSPECTIVES

The analytical approach of inducing a **Typology of Gendered Pipelines** from real country and institutional cases, and looking at the level and range of costs that these three Types assemble on three different entity levels (science/institution/individual worker) has allowed us to re-orientate the more classic vision upon leaky pipelines. We have identified a common foundation of interrelated phenomena across all case studies. More importantly however, we have identified that these common interrelated phenomena appear despite, or because of specific contextual, organisational and configurational compositions. What we can discern is that this composition is quite significant in identifying the level and range of costs that leaky pipelines can incur upon the three entity levels. And that there are significant differences in the interstructuralization of these compositions that generate different kinds, levels and range of costs. Importantly, there are clear indications, inferred from the idea of costs that institutions can counteract towards reducing these cumulative and specific costs, and that they take their share in responsibilities about career opportunities and what becomes more significant, in the organizing of work.

On the individual level, we can identify how in the Type (1), women have a very precarious overall situation, which shows high risk-and precipice in order to continue upon this linear career path, with a lot of personal costs (health, maternity, professional development, stabilization, recognition) and less possibilities and opportunities for rebounding or for catching the fall. We can speak about a high degree of gender inequality for early career women researchers/academics, compared to their male peers. In the Type (2), in terms of gender inequality, balancing is more difficult to achieve for women compared to their male counterparts. In this type, there is more ambiguity and a harder to achieve precarious balance, with the need of the “right” configurations, which are harder to come by for women than for their male peers. In the Type (3) women early researchers and academics have a harder time juggling with many things at the same time than their male counterparts; like in the Type (2), there is a hard to achieve balance between work and family life, with overwork and omnipresence in a exclusive and elitist organization.

What this analysis has shown through looking at costs upon the three level entities, is that this gender inequality impacts upon the macro level of science as much as upon the institution within which it is based. On the level of science as a collaborative, collective work and product of an organization, we can see repercussions that have a significant impact upon the balance that arguably needs to be achieved between the key underlying priorities, missives and motivations of “responsible” science (Despret and Stengers, 2011; Fassa, 2013). For example, important scientific exchanges and development between teaching and research may suffer, as teaching is undervalued both on institutional levels and on the level of the individual researchers. The sticky floor of teaching experienced and lived by mainly female early researchers in short-term contracts and assistantship positions, which are not remunerated similarly nor institutionally recognized as full academic posts, does not allow for teaching to have the same value, both institutional and professional (making sense of ones’ work as meaningful and recognized), and as a consequence can be side-tracked, undervalued and decoupled from research, which in its turn is focussed upon hyper productivity and career orientation. This is also the case for the Types (2) and (3). This devaluing of teaching moreover is parallel to a rising number of students in the very same institutions, where per student-teacher ratio is lower. This means that on the institutional level, there is a bid for students, without a real thought given about the teaching body and its stabilization, motivation, assistance, formation etc. This decoupled way of organizing teaching and research can therefore have important outcomes. There is also an increased short-term research and knowledge production with the rise of short-term research contracts, fraught with limits in time dedicated to fundamental research, coupled with a lesser governmental funding of fundamental research. Early researchers and academics spend also a lot of time bidding for external funding, making the competition more stringent between them, but also making less time for developing research works. Arguably, this reduces the depth of research undertaken, as researchers/academics juggle with more deadlines and hyper productivity in terms of publications. The temporariness of research affects the quality of research outputs and the type of knowledge elaborated in academia.

In all three types of gendered pipeline, there grows a large number of non-stabilized, “floating” not fully integrated research body and assistantship teaching staff, with lesser social and pension schemes in the Type (1), and which are not recognized: for the institution as whole, and for science

to benefit from a collaborative, satisfied through meaningful and recognized working body, it is important to include and recognize short-term employees, as well as permanent assistantship employees. Institutions can therefore benefit from thinking about a greater recognition of doctoral and postdoctoral researchers, as well as assistants; the recognition being multiple in the way of institutional membership, professional development, remuneration, status, social and pension schemes and integration/participation on the level of units (centres, faculties).

We are also looking at lesser diversity in research and teaching in terms of gender, with fewer female role models, and the overall persistence of masculine-based scientific research work model, despite the feminisation of higher education in all three Types. The institutions can ask themselves whether this model really mirrors what kind and form of scientific knowledge they are producing. In the Type (3), research and teaching would continue to be produced by an elite, more homogenous group of researchers/academics, continuing the Ivory Tower effect. In all three types, we can also speak about brain drain for academia and other sectors, because although there has been a feminised higher education, there remain little career chances in academia and also simultaneously little conversion of PhD in SSH sectors outside of academia in the labour market of the Type (1). In the Types (2) and (3), the extra academic labour market is more open to highly skilled workers, male and female but without a real recognition of the PhD level. This raises questions about a decrease in the purpose and value of the PhD. The same institutions are accepting many doctoral and postdoctoral researchers, but with what aim? Moreover, the persisting gender stereotypes in STEM and SSH in all three Types continues to raise questions. Institutions, research and teaching units can benefit by rethinking their purposes of their degrees, their doctoral and postdoctoral appointments, with more responsible and long term vision in making choices, promoting, fostering and guiding strategically.

The Type (1) institution and scientific community are arguably contributing to produce a contradiction between work and family, as women struggle to keep up family and careers, renouncing to parenthood more than men. This is paired with no effective childcare and elderly support system in society at large, and not taken into consideration upon the institutional level. In the Type (2) and (3), we can see the appearance of parental ambiguity, with women having a harder time to keep the balance, with a high dependence upon the right configurations, and feelings of guilt at work and off work. The vertical glass ceiling the higher we climb, which persists in all three types, but especially in Type (3) shows how “keeping up the balance” depends on a high number of favourable configurations that are very hard to come by for women, making the progression in the career as arduous as entering it, especially for professorship, full professorship, management and leadership positions. We can ask ourselves, do research institutions want to contribute to this work logic, reinforcing certain types of profiles based on masculine models, and to a logic of work over care? Mountz et al. (2015) in their collective plea for slow scholarship, speak about how “care work is work”. They explain how systematically marginalizing care “furthers the myth that our successes are achieved as autonomous individuals and, as such, we have no responsibility to share the fruits of our success with others or to dedicate public resources to the work of care” (Lawson 2007, 5: in Mountz et al., 2015: 1238). Care can therefore be part of instead of being alien to the work ethics, logics and organization of institutions. Work demands, conditions, times and nature, and care demands, conditions, times and nature can have a more pronounced place and be taken into consideration in institutional regulation, in unit philosophies, in recruitment criteria and processes.

We can see overall for all types, the high significance of funding systems upon gender inequality, and for all three entity levels. Due to the type of funding systems (point- and closed envelop systems), students are attracted due to a bid for governmental funding, which reinforces a competition over collaboration culture for units and amongst individuals. Moreover, women early researchers and academics have a harder time obtaining funding. In all three types, there is a lesser teacher/student ratio, and more degrees are being given, with lesser quality of teaching programmes. Similar issues of the devaluing of teaching can be addressed for this type also as a result of funding systems. There is lesser governmental funding, especially in SSH (see per student funding for SSH and STEM). We can also say that scientific production is governed by funding structures, because there is lesser fundamental research, and lesser funding for SSH research and teaching. One avenue for institutions and units (teaching and research) to counteract being governed by funding is to reduce competition-based culture and work orientations, and reinforce collaborative work and bid for funding. Units can be more collective about sharing their knowledge amongst themselves, looking for ways to promote this research, and looking for ways to collectively move forward to develop their research. Arguably, this would make lesser lonely heroes and

heroines, and also avoid replications, disjointedness and dispersions of funding applications within and between centres and units.

One major element that plays strongly upon creating costs on all three levels are the gaps between formal and informal criteria, not in terms of their existence, but in terms of tensions of visibility, of clarity, of demands, of discursive resources and making sense of work. There is in all three types, an institutional ambivalence and discrepancy of what can be called formal, or competition-based, or internationally orientated criteria, and of informal, subjective, local nomination-based or integration-based criteria for nomination during recruitment procedures. The struggle for women in this is a balance between the rock and a hard place, because the formal criteria are often hyper productivity (high-ranking, numerous publications...) and mobility based, which are difficult for women to keep up with during childbearing and rearing years. Moreover, they are difficult because publication systems are often intimately linked to network access and possibilities of authorship, both of which are reduced for female early researchers. The second type of criteria that are more local or institutional are strongly linked to access to institutional knowledge, codes, networks (both national and international) and gatekeepers/mentors. This again is a configuration that is less often achieved for early career researchers that are women, as we are also looking at the existence of cooptation logics, lesser female role models and mentors, less support... For career progression moreover, there is the importance of local embeddedness and an overall institutional (all-round academic) implication, omnipresence that is more difficult for women, except with again the “right” configurations coming together (institutional support, private support).

Here the importance of a two-fold process concerning institutions can be addressed: the importance of rethinking criteria, and of rendering the local criteria more clear, visible and recognized, and of rendering the formal criteria more sensitive to counter effects of hyper productivity and mobility demands. Moreover, it becomes important to reconsider the side effects of already existing gender equality measures, such as funding possibilities or mentoring programmes, which are still recruiting “excellence” that is still based on hyper productivity and omnipresence (being constantly available) based criteria (high level and number of publications in renowned journals, mobility), and becoming aware that this is reinforcing competition culture as opposed to a more work healthy collaborative culture. In general, the kind of work culture and organisation can be rethought in favour of work rhythms and philosophy that makes sense to its workers. Mountz et al. (2015) speak about how the intention to slow down aims to undo some of the consequences of the frenetic pace of many of our lives. According to Honoré (2005, 14, in Mountz et al., 2015), “Fast and Slow do more than just describe a rate of change” rather, they are “ways of being, or philosophies of life ...It is about making real and meaningful connections – with people, culture, work, food, everything. The paradox is that Slow does not always mean slow” (Honoré, 2005, 14-15). Hartman and Darab (2012) call for slow scholarship as a response to the acceleration of academic work, discussing in particular the implications of this intensification for pedagogy. They frame intellectual freedom as the “freedom to think” (Hartman and Darab, 2012, 53), a reconceptualization that they note requires the space, time, and other resources curtailed with the escalation of corporate approaches to teaching and university management. Mountz et al. (2015) promote that by slowing down – to listen and read what others have to say, to expand our experiences by getting out of offices and classrooms – we can do our best scholarship, teaching, and mentoring (Moss et al., 1999). “We learn by living. As Lawson (2007) argues, we all require care and care for others, yet this caring happens in private spaces under confining institutions. Living in the world reveals the institutions and policies we need to change and how. Living with and responding to the needs of others keeps us relevant (and human) in ways that no metric can measure. This caring needs to come out of hiding in private times and spaces” (Mountz et al., 2015: 1247).

6. BIBLIOGRAPHY

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7. APPENDIX: VIGNETTES OF LEAKY PIPELINES IN SIX EUROPEAN COUNTRIES

This Appendix compiles six vignettes of each of the Garcia participants' case studies. These vignettes are composed of results from different reports that can contribute to a more comprehensive analysis of the leaky pipeline and interrelated phenomena; the macro-sociological report on Gender and Welfare regimes (D3.2, Le Feuvre, 2015); the quantitative report on leaky pipeline and interrelated phenomena with national and organizational indicators (D6.1, Dubois-Shaik, Fusulier 2015); the qualitative report on leaky pipeline based on interview analysis of three subgroups, movers/leavers, postdocs and newly tenured (D6.2, 2016); the report on recruitment processes and deconstruction of excellence (D7.1, Herschberg et al. 2015, D7.2, Herschberg et al. 2016); the report on gender budgeting, management and decision-making (D5.2, Steinhorsdottir et al. 2016). The purpose of these vignettes is to synthesize all the results in gaining a deeper and more holistic understanding of the leaky pipelines and interrelated phenomena operating in the different country, organizational and departmental contexts. The wordings and phrasing was kept as close as possible to the different partners' own texts.

Vignette 1: Italy – University of Trento

Italy – University of Trento

Overall Characteristics: High job and contractual insecurity, however tilted toward feeling secure despite fixed-term contracts due to assistant professorship position; sticky floor of undervalued teaching; parenthood non-compatible, majority of women who are in research/academia renounce maternity.

Gender and Welfare Regimes: Traditional gender roles, academic/scientific women without children are numerous.

Notwithstanding the advances of recent decades, the economic participation rate of women is still considerably lower than that of men in Italy. In 2014 the country continued to be among the worst performers in the Global Gender Gap Index (ranking 69th out of 142 overall), penalized above all by the economic participation and opportunity category (114th), while the gap in educational attainment was narrower (62th). Italy lags behind in women's access to the labour market, remuneration, career advancement, promotion to positions of leadership and new business initiatives. The education gap had been closed. Less marked, but still observable, is the traditional concentration of women graduates in education and humanities while engineering remains the only male-dominated field or study. Gender gaps in the labour market are still large. Female employment rates remain low, especially in Southern Italy and in general for women with low education. Young women are more likely than young men to be unemployed, to be employed in less stable forms of employment and in the lowest-paid sectors (horizontal segregation). Lack of services for children (and above all for the elderly) combined with rigid work arrangements make it hard to reconcile work and family life. Female unemployment rates are higher than male rates; career progress is difficult; and young women are over-represented in atypical and precarious jobs, with limited protection in case of maternity. A policy mix comprising access to standard jobs (good quality, open-ended positions), affordable childcare, neutral tax and benefit systems, flexible working time arrangements and the provision of paid leave for both parents could support them in reconciling work and family and effectively promote female employment.

Women's position in Italian society has been deeply affected by socio-cultural changes and European Union requirements since the beginning of the 1970s. However, transformations in the structures of the society have not been always consistent with it. Political parties were slow to respond to the requests of civil society movements including women's movement. The persistence and the dominance of a conservative and traditional political discourse has meant the difficulties to promote norms, legislation and measures aimed to promote women's roles other than the 'caring role' and their presence in all the fields of society.

The problem of efficient institutional mechanisms for promoting, enacting and monitoring legislation on gender equality in Italy has never been satisfactorily solved at the national level of central government, as witnessed by the variety of solutions adopted over the years. The Department for Equal Opportunities, established in 1997 has been headed by various Ministers (nine ministers in 18 years), whose action has always been impaired by lack of resources, short terms of office and sometimes even lack of experience in gender issues. The importance of gender inequality vs. other grounds of discriminations has been interpreted by each minister very differently, according to political parties' membership, culture and openness to civil society.

Academic careers have undergone profound changes in the access and promotion rules. Since these processes have gone hand in hand with the drastic reduction in the available financial resources, the consequences at the individual and structural level are ambivalent and the current situation of the Italian university system is quite alarming: i) over one third of the university research staff has a non-permanent position; these positions are all concentrated among the new generation of researchers; ii) the severe budget cuts of the university system produced a serious contraction of permanent teaching staff which negatively affects the current efficiency of the university, both in

teaching and research activities; iii) the new rules seems not to reduce the female disadvantage in the career advancement (at least in the short run).

Previous or existing gender policies: Limited gender policies, mainly addressed to employees; PhD students and postdocs only partially included. No mentoring programmes.

Quantitative phenomena, missions and task balance: Leaky pipeline, sticky floor, glass ceiling, postdoc bottleneck.

- Data confirm that women employed in the Italian academic system take more time than men to enter tenured positions. This dynamic seems almost stable over time – for the transition to both associate professorships and full professorships – and across fields of study.

- Teaching considered as sticky floor.

Early stages scientific careers in Italy are characterized by:

- The persistence and reproduction of gender asymmetries already at the early stages of career after PhD graduation.

- The rise of the level of precariousness and job instability experienced by the new generation of PhD holders.

- An increased level of competition for permanent positions that in turn follows from the inability of the University system to absorb the rising numbers of PhD holders, from the limited development of research positions in other sectors as well as from the low level of employability of doctorate holders outside academia.

- The persistence of disadvantages suffered by women both in terms of scientific productivity and during selection processes.

- The temporariness of research affects the quality of research outputs and the type of knowledge elaborated in academia.

The picture drawn in this work confirms a core statement of the leaky pipeline and glass ceiling debates. Also in the case examined the under-representation of women is drastically chronic and it will hardly self-correct in the foreseeable future (Badaloni et al. 2011; Frattini and Rossi 2012; Martucci 2011) nor it will naturally disappear over time as the numbers of women increase in the entry levels (Palomba 2001; EU 2013).

Already at early career stages, women employment positions are less stable and less paid than male ones and are more influenced by family and personal situations. These weaknesses are generally more evident in the STEM disciplines, but also the SSH fields, where women are more represented, are not immune from unfair mechanisms that foster processes of exclusion of women from career advancements, governing bodies and positions of power.

At the institutional level, few measures are essential for improving women's status in scientific career (Etzkowitz and Ranga 2011b):

- changing recruitment, retention and assessment processes so that Universities are more transparent;

- providing equal support for men and women involved in scientific activities at every stage;

- including women in mentoring, peer review and research funding applications, gender monitoring and regular publishing of funding statistics, differentiated by discipline and research instrument.

Growing levels of precariousness and instability in the early stages of career, together with the low chances to obtain a permanent position inside the academic system, rise the necessity to support PhD holders to develop skills and competencies able to support inter-sectorial careers as well as to find effective strategies to give continuity to their personal career paths. The main idea is to overcome the **linear (academic) path that underpins the leaky pipeline metaphor**, moving to a non-linear model of careers across other sectors, new occupations and professions requiring scientific and research expertise (Vanish Box model) (Etzkowitz and Ranga 2011a). The general vulnerability of postdoctoral positions ("assegnisti di ricerca") needs to be limited starting first and foremost from a redefinition of their ambiguous contractual condition. A first progress would be the inclusion of this position among the ones entitled to receive (at least) unemployment benefits, in order to better manage the high-level uncertainty that characterises (the early stages of) scientific careers.

Qualitative Results:

Postdocs:

- Parenthood considered incompatible.

- All issues related to contractual instability seem to affect more the postdocs at the DSRS than those at the DISI. Such difference is mainly due to the wider range of research chances outside the academic system available in the field of computer science and to the higher future.

- The majority of the stories collected, at the DISI as well as the DSRS, albeit with some differences, stressed the importance of establishing a strong network within the department in which it was hoped to obtain a post, and more generally within the scientific community. Abilities and awards remaining equal, in fact, those more integrated into the research community, those who have the right knowledge and relations both formal and informal, are more visible to the decision-makers in selection procedures for postdocs and assistant professors. Upward mobility in academia is often a 'sponsored mobility' (Kanter, 1977) in which the mentor's role is crucial.

- Postdocs in STEM describe more stability and job satisfaction at the prospect of moving into private sector.

Newly Tenured:

Existence of fixed-term assistant professors: the group of fixed-term assistant professors (in both departments) do not see the expiring of their contract as problematic. This group perceive themselves as part of the university community and assume that, given their current position and the internal recruitment/career advancement rules at the UNITN, they have high chances to obtain a permanent position in the short run within the department where they are working in.

- Female parenthood incompatible:

At the same time, female assistant professors showed a higher level of dissatisfaction and intolerance with the “long hours” culture” characterizing the current university system and with the difficulty to reconcile their private and family lives with their work when compared with their male colleagues and with (fe)male postdocs.

At both the DISI and the DSRS, and in all three groups of respondents, the women more often than the men emphasised a lack of cooperation. As pointed out elsewhere (Kantola, 2008), the lack of cooperation experienced by women can signal a form of subtle discrimination, which may fuel dynamics of marginalization. Not feeling integrated into a research group, the women experience a kind of isolation that puts them at a disadvantage. The lack of cooperation among the members of the research team may also create further difficulty in understanding the informal rules of the game that one must know to progress in a scientific career.

Finally, a further issue in regard to which significant gender differences were described, albeit with different positions in the departments studied, was invisible and undervalued work. Administrative and undervalued tasks.

Movers/Leavers:

- Job security/work-life balance: Among leavers, finding a job outside the academia/research sector is a way to reduce the interference of work on their life, reduce the pace of work, reconquer a balance between private life and work, and limit professional dissatisfaction and the lack of perspective experienced in the academic sector. However, in the case of female leavers, the new working position is often described as under-qualified with respect to their level of education and they continue to show low levels of satisfaction about their professional situation.

- Among movers and postdocs, it is possible to identify some career paths that, more than others, seem to foster and enhance their long term career perspectives in the research sector. More precisely, early career researchers who have moved abroad and, only in the case of the STEM department, who are working or are planning to work in the private sector describe such job positions as more qualified, stable and better paid than those experienced in the Italian academy. Moreover, these positions are considered as an efficient way to improve both their professional skills, and their long term career perspectives and free time for their private life as well.

Recruitment and discursive resources:

What emerges by the analysis of the actual practices adopted in the two departments considered, is that all the procedure’s steps are characterized by ambivalences amid which the committee members try to identify the most suitable – or the most accountable – candidate. In both departments’ practices we noted a discrepancy between the formal and the actual criteria used for the selections. At the Department of Sociology and Social Research, a first ambivalence concerns the apparent contradiction between the bureaucratic and the business-like logics that inspire the new norms of RTD recruitment, where the necessary accountability of the overall procedure can contrast with the department’s discretionary final power of choice. The same ambivalence shapes the relations between the role of the committee and the strategic choices of the department within the procedure, with the risk of clashes between the committee’s evaluation and the decisions taken by the departmental board. At the Department of Information Engineering and Computer Sciences formal criteria are utilised as a first objective selection of the candidates. Being strictly defined by quantitative indexes, parameters and rankings, this first stage of evaluation allows, in the board members’ opinion, the equality of shortlists. Hence, the subjective aspects of evaluation are used in a second stage on a range of high qualified candidates. Even if some of these arguments are present also in the interviews about post-doctoral selections, it is clear that in these situations the criteria of choice are more focused on the specific necessities of the research programmes. The concept of excellence is not often used by the interviewees of both departments, and in some cases it is even critically considered, because of its vagueness and abstraction. However, when it is used, it is mainly referred to internationality (publications, networks and experiences), autonomy, and high quality of research and scientific activities. Finally, gender equality is not considered to be an issue for meritocracy. Although gender bias is recognized, at the same time it is delegated to the broader society: the only gender-related problem, and always referred to women, is the lack of social services for motherhood and children, while the possibility that an organisational culture influences recruitment procedures within academia was not considered by almost all the interviewees.

Organisational Modalities:

The University’s vision and mission fall in line with the Italian/European dominant rhetoric of the needed changes and new challenges of universities. The key words used in the University Strategic Plan are: interdisciplinarity, internationalisation, innovation and knowledge transfer. These imply: the importance of the University participation in the economic development at the global and local level; the production of innovation and new knowledge for the enterprises and the necessity of overcoming the borders among the disciplines in order to tackle the challenges of a complex society. Moreover, the University Strategic Plan lists a large number of actions and indexes, but this is not a well-integrated document in comparison with the Strategic Plans of the Departments (e.g. the DISI and the DSRS Strategic Plans) that contain more concrete proposal and the definition of specific targets to achieve. Data relating to gender distribution in higher and management positions at the University of Trento show a strong gender imbalance. Even if the Rector and the General Director were women, the problem of vertical

segregation is still present in the majority of the governing bodies of the institution. Not only, as the Glass Ceiling Index (2.2) highlights, few women occupy high positions in the academic career ladder, but also, in the selected departments, very few women are involved in the managing bodies of research and teaching activities - phenomenon that is even more visible at the DISI because of the low presence of women in permanent academic positions. Although gender and equality issues seem to be taken in charge by the institution, policies and concrete consequences are not visible. In other words, the formal recognition of this situation does not affect women conditions in terms of recruitment, promotion and representation. Moreover, the effectiveness of the incentive policy to encourage academic structures (Departments and Centres) to contribute to the gender balance in terms of full and associate professors has not been evaluated yet. University of Trento's financial data are available on the annual financial statement published on the website and main data about students and academic staff are available in the intranet Athenaeum or easily trackable thanks to the statistical office. The administrative offices were helpful in order to collect information about the criteria used for the allocation of the resources at university and department level. Therefore, the transparency level of the university seems to be good, except, for a lack of transparency in the internal competitive calls: the definition of the criteria, their application, the referees' nomination and results published are not totally intelligible.

The postdocs and fixed-term assistant professors' work conditions are not taken in charge by the institutional representative we interviewed. Indeed, this is problem of the whole Italian academic system, difficult to be tackled at the local level. Postdoctoral researchers are not hired – and they are not considered – as employees of the institutions and in most cases they do not have access to University benefits and services as those who have permanent positions. The Directors of selected Departments underline the impossibility to plan the recruitment and the promotion of fixed-term researchers because of the lack of resources. They state that this situations affects – and will affect – the university system as a whole, and the younger generation of researchers in terms of career opportunities, work (e.g. importance for national and international mobility) and life conditions (e.g. family, health, etc.).

Vignette 2: Iceland – University of Iceland

Iceland-University of Iceland

Overall Characteristics:

Strong masculine habitus and difficulty of “straying” from a lone and overengaged path; de-centralisation on the level of decision-making and financial management, overwork, work-orientated logic especially during postdoc, glass ceiling persists despite higher equality in numbers overall, persisting gender stereotypes in fields (SSH female/STEM male), especially SSH key aspects are importance of parenthood/family for an ambivalent attitude of women) whereas STEM are more often non-parents/ Matilda effect/co-optation logic/figure of “ideal or all-round academic”

Gender and Welfare regimes: Traditional gender roles, masculinized breadwinner/feminized carer

According to the World Economic Forum (2013) Iceland passes as a leading example of gender equality. The rich participation of women on the labour market is often interpreted as de facto equality. Despite high gender equality ranking, gender equality laws and machinery large gender disparities remain. Women are largely underrepresented in decision making positions, in politics and finance. Overall, a gendered pay gap is a persistent problem.

Gender equality in the field of science and research in Iceland is structured by law, resolutions and equality work. Overall, both law and policies broadly cover the structural presupposition of gender equality within science and research. The implementation law stimulated the increased number of women within the Icelandic academia. At the same time the number of professors employed on permanent basis remains male-biased. Women and men tend to choose gender stereotypical training, study and occupation. Financial resources in academia also seem directed through and to males and male-dominated research fields, preserving a system ranked by and to the favour of men.

The gender-difference in choice of education and occupation has been explained with the social-cultural framework, opportunities and hindrances within the system that favour culturally defined male qualities and dominance. The structural hindrances have, among others, been identified as glass ceilings, leaky pipelines and cultural restraints. The legal framework and increased involvement of women within the community at large is not enough to balance the gendered power-relations within the system. Further development and reinforcement of methods to implement gender equality in the field of science and research is much needed. There is still a long way to go before gender equality is gained.

Previous or existing gender policy: None, now ongoing with gender budgeting, supportive of Garcia marginally; support by individual heads, somewhat strategic support.

Quantitative report phenomena: Leaky Pipeline, glass ceiling, sticky floor, bottle neck doctorate/postdoctorate, STEM/SSH persisting gender stereotypes

When analysing data related to the leaky pipeline at the national level, it is immediately obvious that women, in terms of numbers, dominate higher education. This might appear to be a positive development at first glance, but on closer inspection it is evident that even though women are in the majority, they are so predominantly in SSH

fields, which enjoy the least amount of funding, the highest teacher-to-student ratio (i.e. bigger workload), the least amount of stature, and the fewest options for a future career in academia. Oppositely, STEM fields, which are dominated by men, receive considerably more funding and enjoy a higher stature even though they attract a much lower number of students.

If we move up the academic ladder we also find that men overwhelmingly occupy the higher academic positions with the most stature. It is therefore a distinct possibility that the leaky pipeline to some extent has its roots in broader gender and welfare regimes, where women are traditionally left with the least prestigious societal responsibilities.

Consequently, even though it is important to address the question as to why there are so few women in STEM fields and why women move away from academic careers the higher we get on the career ladder, it is equally important to address the question as why there are so many men. It is possible that, on the macro-level, men might feel a pressure to conform to masculine ideals of stature and prestige and therefore end up choosing a technical field of study in a homo-social environment that is sure to land them a well-paid future job which will confirm their role as family-providers. In the same vein, men might opt out of certain careers in SSH fields because an overarching culture of masculinity does not connect male identity to SSH topics. If we have been able to change science stereotypes in a way so that a woman is now more likely to choose to a line of study within STEM, is it then not possible to change masculine stereotypes so that a man may be less likely to do so and instead move into an SSH related field, which will nurture him with the socially or culturally saturated knowledge for which he craves? A point of self-reflection might be to ask ourselves whether we also fall in the trap of lending more importance to STEM fields, which we have learned to think of as more prestigious and important. Why else would we focus so much on improving the status of women within STEM and not so much men's status within SSH? After all, these fields are of equal importance. Consequently, based on the quantitative data, we recommend implementations that seek to break down stereotypes both within SSH and STEM, not to merely provide equal attention to men in a debate on gender equality in science, but to ensure that men do not flock to STEM fields or avoid certain SSH fields because they are stuck in a rut of traditional masculine ideals.

Qualitative Results:

Postdocs:

Co-optation and “following” a mentor more possible for men, less female “role models”, work life imbalance, productivist culture

Newly Tenured:

While this was also the case among current SSH academics, this group had a tendency to downplay these problems. Across many SSH interviews, workloads and resulting work/life balance issues were emphasized.

Movers/Leavers:

While there were of course exceptions in all cases, there was still a clear sense among SSH movers/leavers that workloads were a big problem with real consequences for academics and their families. Only a few participants among our STEM movers/leavers counted workloads and work/life balance issues among reasons to leave academia.

For instance, if movers/leavers women told stories about how men with fewer qualifications than them had been hired in their stead or how they needed to work harder to obtain the same influence as their male colleagues, none men told these stories, which underlines the gendered urgency of this possible Matilda effect.

Recruitment and discursive resources:

There are clear differences observed between the formal and actual practises within SSH and STEM. Informal criteria, such as “communication skills”, are now in most cases in the job description. One can say that the informal criteria are therefore in disguise as formal criteria. The in/formal criteria “communication skills” cannot be found as criteria in regulations but is of high importance in the actual practices within STEM and SSH. The formal criteria of administration experience seem not to weight at all in the actual practices, it is considered a plus if a candidate has such experience but it is not a minus if a candidate does not have it. The formal criteria of teaching experience does not seem to be of much importance in the actual practices. In STEM it is viewed as something you can learn on the go and in SSH you have to show you can teach but the number of courses, or the amount of experience does not seem to matter. Despite both Schools belonging to the University of Iceland, there were also clear differences observed between the schools of SSH and STEM with regard to appointment practises. When comparing the actual practices of SSH and STEM, there is much more emphasis on excellence in STEM. This is notable in their emphasis on which university the candidate graduated from, on post-doc fellowship/s, on the number of published articles and number of publications in journals in the ISI-database. The committee members in STEM think that the department should not appoint candidates if they aren't excellent enough, while in SSH this does not seem to be the case. In SSH a post-doc fellowship isn't even mentioned. Fitting into the team, or being a “team member”, comes up both in SSH and STEM. In STEM the focus is that academics need to work together doing research and therefore it is important that the candidate fits into the team. In SSH the academics seem to work more alone because a candidate that brings something new, they talk about wanting “diversity” of research fields within the department, therefore the emphasis is more that the candidate has to fit in the group socially because it seems that the academics won't work that much together on research projects.

When it comes to gender, there is a clear difference between STEM and SSH. In STEM they seem to have no interest in gender or the gender equality policy of the University of Iceland. In STEM they state that gender is not an important criteria. In SSH they speak more about gender, and all committee members knew of and most had read

the equal rights policy of the University of Iceland. When discussing gender the committee members usually start talking about equality for men or other marginalized groups. Also, the committee members had the urge to explain or even defend themselves, or the department, when it comes to gender equality.

Organisational features/modalities: de-centralisation of university from international market, internal logic, linked to geographic, linguistic and ethnic context.

This objective of this report was to obtain insight into the managerial and financial framework of University of Iceland, and examine the decision-making and budgeting processes from a gender perspective. Special focus on two academic schools, STEM and SSH and on conditions for academic careers for newcomers in academia. Internationalization, competition and performance orientation are all seen as essential factors on University of Iceland's road towards excellence. Our findings reveal that the managerial decision and corporate instruments used at the University are more favourable for research within STEM oriented subjects, rather than the research within SSH oriented subjects, and that also applies to the conditions for teaching. The decision and instruments are perceived as objective and gender neutral, and ignore that by rewarding fields that are male dominated the current system increases indirect gender discrimination in academia. In terms of research, the university encourages faculties to engage in research related activities and depending on their performance the faculties receive additional allocation, which is taken from the governmental appropriation. With the public funding being a 'zero sum game' the university tampers with the teaching part of the distribution formula to make ends meet, the financial compensation for these rewarded research activities therefore affect the allocation for other activities, such as teaching. Faculties that are more teaching oriented therefore are denied this financial compensation based on this criterion. Allocation to the faculties for research related activities is based on three elements: the number of graduates with masters and PhD degrees, academic staffs' performance in research and the faculty's success in raising third-party-funding. All these elements give STEM faculties more advantage than SSH faculties. First, STEM graduates considerably more PhD candidates annually and the PhD duration is shorter. Secondly, assessments of academics staffs' performance in research is built on STEM focused criteria and traditions, such as the amount of attained international competitive funding, publications in international 'excellent' and 'superior' journals and multi-authorship on publications. Thirdly, faculty's success in raising third-party funding, when STEM has significantly more projects funded than SSH.

When it comes to teaching, the state's funding formula for teaching rewarding almost 60-100% higher funding towards the academic institution for full-time equivalent STEM students than full-time equivalent SSH students. When allocating funding to the academic schools UI keeps the same proportions for academic fields. SSH has indeed a lot higher number of students than STEM, but due to lower funding per full-time equivalent student the school has difficulties with hiring full time academic staff. This becomes apparent when we look at the student/full-time teacher ratio, which is almost double in SSH than in STEM. Not only does this system affect the distribution of funding and academic fields differently, the evaluation and incentive system directly affects the individual academic working within SSH and STEM. The research points, especially the major points, affect the academics' opportunity to promotion, prestige and salaries. STEM academics get on average 27% more research points than SSH academics and the average number of major points per academic staff in STEM occupies higher positions than the academic staff in SSH. This indicates that the academics in STEM are more active researchers or that the evaluation system is more favourable to STEM. The evaluation system acknowledges research activities but undervalues teaching and the heavy workload that academics' have to put up with, especially within SSH faculties, where the student/full-time teacher ratio is the highest. The fact that STEM academics have more major points than SSH academics indicates that the requirement to reach a minimum amount of major points will be more difficult for an assistant professor in SSH than in STEM. In addition, STEM acknowledges the heavy workload of teaching by giving their newly hired assistant professors teaching discount and funding to supporting them on their quest of acquiring the minimum amount of major points. The funding that STEM receives, both the public and third party funding, gives STEM the flexibility to make support like this possible, that however is not possible within the financial framework of SSH. Research activities and academic position determine the academics' chance of funding. With that as a factor for success in attaining funding, then the system of distributing the grants is STEM- and male focussed. The majority of the research points and major points go to STEM and with vertical segregation prevailing in both academic schools, most of the academics occupying the position of full professor are men. In addition, this funding system also affects newcomers in academia but the conditions are different in STEM and SSH. Academics that attain funding can hire PhD students and Post-docs, and as a result most PhD students in STEM have funding, which is not the case for SSH. We see that the duration of SSH PHD programme is on average longer than the duration of STEM PhD programme and funding plays a big part in that. The longer the duration of the PhD the more expensive it is for the faculty and for the student.

By using the first stage of gender budgeting and critically analysing the state of University of Iceland, we have demonstrated that male-dominated and female-dominated fields are impacted differently by the policies and systems to distribute funding, in other words we have made an attempt to make inequality at the University visible. The analysis reveals that resources are not distributed in a gender equitable way, it simultaneously creates an opportunity to readdress the inequity and reconstruct academic budgetary policies and resources distribution in order to obtain fairer and equal academia.

Vignette 3: Slovenia - Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts (SSH Department) and University of Ljubljana (DABF) (STEM Department)

Slovenia-Research Centre of Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts/University of Ljubljana

Overall Characteristics: Masculine habitus, co-optation logic, organisational culture of “negative competition”, mainly STEM work/life imbalance

Gender and Welfare regimes:

The report has identified the main characteristics of the welfare system in Slovenia in fields that are relevant for the GARCIA project. It was found that Slovenia has largely preserved the ‘state’ welfare model that was prevalent in the socialist system, although there are indications that also non-profit and profit organisations are gaining increasing importance in providing welfare to citizens.

Special attention was paid to the issue of paid work and family and to their mutual reconciliation and some peculiarities of the system in Slovenia in comparison to other GARCIA countries were identified. High female labour force participation rates are characteristic of Slovenia and a dual-breadwinner model is prevalent. Part-time work is not very common, which holds true also for women with small children who usually continue to work full-time. This is probably required in financial terms and is facilitated by a solid network of institutionalised childcare and extensive family support networks. Nevertheless, as the report pervasively demonstrates, women, in addition to being employed, also take on the majority of family responsibilities, including housework and childcare. Men devote significantly more time to paid work. Although in recent years there are some indications of an increasing involvement of men in parenting and household chores (e.g. the proportion of men taking parental leave, increasing use of paternity leave, division of household tasks, etc.), the ‘traditional’ division of labour at home seems to persist. Based on the data and results of previous research on the subject of (young) women in science, it can be argued that the prevailing life course ‘pattern’ of women scientists is similar to that described above. Although in terms of education, women have achieved almost full equality with men, and even have surpassed men in some fields, men continue to occupy the majority of senior research and managerial positions in science and divisions of ‘typical’ male/female fields of science persist.

From 2011 the (ongoing) crisis-related reforms have highly affected the welfare system, also related to gender. The Fiscal Balance Act (2012) aims at slightly changed family benefits. The eligibility criteria for direct and indirect family benefits like the birth grant (a one-off ‘childbirth allowance’ payment intended to cover some of the costs related to new-borns), child allowance, textbook funds, scholarships, subsidised transport for pupils and students and subsidised school meals were amended. The Fiscal Balance Act addressed the public sector, to which the majority of research and higher education institutions also belong. It blocked promotions of public employees; as a consequence, obtaining a higher academic title does not imply a salary raise. It also restricted new employments in the public sector, limited the length of annual leave as well as payment of annual leave subsidies (regress). Moreover, the Labour Market Regulation Act from 2013 facilitates higher flexibility of the labour force. These recent measures thus additionally challenge the position of women in the academia in Slovenia. As regards to the percentage of employed female researchers, Slovenia fits the general EU pattern (37% of researchers with PhD are female, 20% of women at high academic positions), but the percentage of women occupying decision making positions and managing distribution of resources is significantly lower than the European average (36% EU, 23% Slovenia). Therefore, there are no legal provisions that directly or indirectly would discriminate against women in science. Moreover, the rules of financing of the National research agency account for maternity / paternity leave as one of the factors that could influence research careers and exclude this time from evaluation provisions. However, men largely outnumber women in terms of leading programme groups and in the number of awards received for their scientific work.

The increasing precariousness and insecure job positions in science in Slovenia were identified in existing research, but it seems that more research is needed, in order to identify to what extent this issue is gendered. Existing studies show that female scientists under 40 years of age and with lower academic titles most often perceive gender-related partiality in their academic environment and indicated parenthood as a primary source of such partiality. However, there is a certain gap in knowledge about women and men at early stages of academic careers, and this is an urgent topic to be addressed.

Previous or existing gender policy: None, no mentoring programmes and no gender policy, ongoing through Garcia project but with some institutional resistance.

Quantitative Data: Leaky pipeline, glass ceiling, sticky floor, bottleneck

Key results of quantitative and qualitative analysis: Statistical indicators (2010-2013) and statistical survey data (2012) at the national level clearly show the existence of leaky pipeline in Slovenia, in a 3-dimensional way, namely: first, the share of female students prevails at all study levels (BSc, MSc and PhD), but the share of researchers (PhD holders) employed at academic institutions is in favour of men. Almost ‘traditionally’, there is an unbalanced gender distribution in the scientific field (STEM/SSH). Female students are still overrepresented in the so-called female scientific disciplines, while male students outnumber women in the so-called male scientific disciplines. Agriculture as a scientific discipline is an example of a reversed trend: former masculine field is becoming slightly in favour of female students. Second, a scissor-shaped curve of professional trajectories of women and men proves gendered vertical segregation: the share of women is decreasing in every higher step of academic (promotion) ladder. Third, there are more female PhD holders who are temporarily employed.

The available data of 2 test institutions in the time-period observed (2010-2013) reflects the national picture only in some aspects. Female researchers of all academic levels obtaining temporary and permanent contracts are overrepresented in the SSH Institution (Fran Ramovš Institute of the Slovenian Language ZRC SAZU) compared to men. In another STEM test department (the Department for Agronomy at the Biotechnical Faculty, University of Ljubljana), there are more women among the research staff with permanent and temporary contracts, while the number of male Full and Associate Professors is higher compared to women. Yet, observing promotions and exits, leaky pipeline phenomenon cannot be verified and confirmed at the STEM/SSH Institutions' level, mostly because of a relatively small number of such cases in a relatively short time-period observed (2010-2013). There were 10 exits (6 men and 4 women) at the STEM Department and only 1 male leaver at the SSH institute, and only 2 female promotions at the SSH and 14 promotions (7 men and 7 women) at the STEM Department.

Qualitative results:

Qualitative analysis identified some potential sources for the leaky pipeline phenomenon. The first one is related to poor mentorship experienced in both test institutions. In Slovenia, there is no official mentoring programme with clear protocol and responsibilities defined for mentors. As a result, the interviewees experienced various kind of mentorship, from appropriate step-by-step socialisation into the academic world to the absence of any kind of relationships. All interviewees stressed the importance of mentors in the mentees' trajectories, but their role was particularly emphasised by the involuntary movers and leavers. Both female and male interviewees from this group of collectors were left to themselves and were not adequately integrated into the academic environment. Their mentors did not equip them with necessary advice, support and skills regarding project and article writing as well as building necessary relationships with other associates.

Another source for the leaky pipeline phenomenon pertains to organisational culture. Yet, this source is identified mainly at the STEM test institution. The collectors from all the groups emphasised collegial and cooperative relationships inside the research groups, and distant, detached and 'rivalry' relationships between the research groups or research programmes at the departmental or even faculty level. As possible reasons for such a climate of 'negative competition' they identified imposed scientific excellence criteria defined by the national research agency, which follows the principles of the so-called 'knowledge society'. Instead of interdisciplinary and collaborative efforts and strategies employed at the departmental level, tensions emerged between research groups and their members in constant fights for scarce national and hardly obtained international research funds. The masculine habitus of the scientific field can be recognised in the heads of the Chairs, leaders of research groups and programmes, who, according to the interviewees from the 3 samples, employ the informal rules, strategies and tactics of who at the departmental level is allowed to apply for a project, mentorship and the like.

The Mathilda effect can be recognised at both test institutions, particularly in the involuntary female leavers who were promised to stay at the faculty after their PhDs if they were more engaged in some additional tasks (e.g. project or article writing). The Matilda and the Matthew effect can be recognised in superior-inferior clearly defined tasks as the result of internal politics at both test institutions. The main strategy or politics of superior(s), who is/are the best according to the national scientific excellence criteria, is to supervise and distribute tasks among the lower-ranked associates. According to this practice, the higher-ranked superior(s) is/are involved in financing, while the lower-ranked associates implement all necessary time-consuming tasks in research.

Interviewees' low sensitivity to gender unbalanced position of PhD holders of the observed groups in both test institution is a very important result from the qualitative analysis. Instead, the interviewees from both test institutions stressed a generational difference or gap as more salient, and in the STEM test institution, the interviewees mentioned the 'unfair' difference between the higher academic title obtained and lower-paid-systemised job position.

Difficulties of work and life harmonisation are identified mostly in the STEM competing environment, while at the SSH test institution, this issue was recognised as a challenge only among the leavers/movers.

Unstable financing of research is the biggest risk factor for the leaky pipeline in both STEM and SSH institutions. Yet, it is also worth mentioning that, at the moment, the leaky pipeline is not so much visible among the stayers of the selected SSH Institute because of their currently secured jobs and financing. Still, the younger generation is afraid of possible changed circumstances, which may also lead towards the leaky pipeline. They are not well prepared for project applications and their publication record is poor according to the scientific excellence criteria. Finally, the majority of them have not yet been a project leader.

Postdocs: Few mentors or guidance for females. See above.

Newly Tenured: organisational culture. Yet, this source is identified mainly at the STEM institution. A climate of 'negative competition' is highlighted and connected to scientific excellence criteria defined by the national research agency, which follows the principles of the so-called 'knowledge society'. Tensions emerged between research groups and their members in constant fights for scarce national and hardly obtained international research funds. This masculine habitus can be recognised in the heads of the Chairs, leaders of research groups and programmes. The main strategy or politics of superiors, who are the best according to the national scientific excellence criteria, is to supervise and distribute tasks among the lower-ranked associates. According to this practice, the higher-ranked superiors are involved in financing, while the lower-ranked associates implement all necessary time-consuming tasks in research. This is a condition of production of a Matilda effect.

-Difficulties of work and life harmonisation are identified mostly in the STEM competing environment,

Movers/leavers: qualitative analysis identified some potential sources for the leaky pipeline phenomenon. The first one is related to poor mentorship experienced in both test institutions. There is no official mentoring programme with clear protocol and responsibilities defined for mentors. As a result, the interviewees experienced various kind

of mentorship, from appropriate step-by step socialisation into the academic world to the absence of any kind of relationships. All interviewees stressed the importance of mentors in the mentees' trajectories, but their role was particularly emphasized by the involuntary movers and leavers. Both female and male interviewees from this group of interviewees were left to themselves and were not adequately integrated into the academic environment. Their mentors did not equip them with necessary advice, support and skills regarding project and article writing as well as building necessary relationships with other associates.

- Difficulties of work and life harmonisation are identified mostly in the STEM competing environment, while at the SSH institution, this issue was recognised as a challenge only among the leavers/movers.

Recruitment and discursive resources:

The gap between formal criteria and actual practices is strongly related to the fact that for T/FP positions formal requirement process is rather an exception. These positions are under the promotion system where academic personnel progress from one rank to another. In the case of SSH which is not university, but research centre with 'project-based' work, in rare cases when there is a new job vacancy, these are the people already planned in the project proposal and once the financing of the project is accepted, they are formally employed for the duration of the project. As for STEM, these are people who entered into Department as PhD students (as teaching assistants) or were already engaged to work on projects. In both STEM and SSH in the case of postdocs (which is, as explained on p. 3, rather specific position in Slovenian context), again there is no formal procedure and the HR official informs the Employment Service of Slovenia about the announcement of job vacancy for the already known candidate without any detailed job description and requirements. In such cases, there are no other candidates except the only one 'known candidate' and no commission is organised.

It seems that there is no clear boundary between formal criteria and actual practices. Since there is often no 'formal recruitment process', the selection of a candidate is made only through actual practices and undefined (abstract) criteria. In general, in both STEM and SSH interviewees, a personal experience in work with a candidate is a decisive criterion in selection procedure, an assurance that a selected candidate would fit in to a team group. In the cases where the formal procedure takes place, at first formal criteria are examined. Then, it is decisive whether the committee members know the candidate or have working experiences with them.

In terms of affirmative action and gender equality policies, neither in formal criteria nor in the actual practices gender is particularly acknowledged. Regarding formal criteria, only for the position of Young Researcher (without PhD) the eligibility criteria, for candidates who used maternity leave, the age/number of years limit from receiving MA or BA degree is lifted for 1 year for each child. The same is applicable for documented sick leaves that were longer than 6 months. The appointment reports in both STEM and SSH do not anyhow refer to or deal with affirmative action or gender equality.

All interviewees believe that gender is relevant only as a factor in making a balanced research teams. Gender balanced groups are presented as more desirable. They agree that the departments, chairs and research groups have to be gender balanced. In STEM, they consider that it is necessary to introduce a policy in order to stimulate women not at the beginning of their academic career, but later. On the contrary, in SSH department they believe this is not necessary since women are more typical candidates in the current tendency of employment of young people at the beginning of their career.

Organisational features/modalities:

Presented data shows that in both organisations women are less engaged in the higher decision-making and managerial positions. However, in the case of the ZRC (SSH) the gender structure is much more balanced while for BF (STEM), we can talk about the glass ceiling phenomenon. This also proves a need of increasing proportional inclusion of women in decision-making positions and leadership. Regarding decision-making, in both ZRC and BF, on the main leading positions, (Director and Dean) are men, yet in the case of BF, the Faculty management is also men-only. Regarding the management structure, in the case of ZRC the management consists of 5 members, 1 man and 4 women, which can be seen as women-dominated, while for the Governing Board, as the main decision-making body proves to be men-dominated (4 women members and 6 men members). The gender structure of Heads of research institutes is more gender balanced and has changed only little in the last 4 years; in 2013, there were 10 women Heads of research institutes and 8 men Heads of research institutes. Regarding STEM, Governing Board is also men-dominated (in years 2010 and 2011 there were 5 men and 2 women members, from 2012 there is 21 woman left and 6 men members), which is the same in the case of Heads of the Departments. Where we can track the changes in the direction of more gender-balanced structure is the Faculty Senate in favour of greater representation of women comparatively in 4 years.

Both organisations are mostly publicly funded, but there is a different in the level of autonomy: ZRC has the autonomy according to national legislation about public (research) organisations and national legislation about public financing and financing of public research projects, while for BF funding the Faculty for pedagogical work by the University is centrally allocated. Therefore, the faculty has some minimal or no autonomy in this regard. ZRC is a research institution and its financing depends on the success at the governmental call for research projects (from the Slovenian Research Agency) that depends on governmental research policy and national budget planning; In that sense, ZRC experiences constant insecurity regarding funding since budget can be changed annually in accordance with the public finances. BF is funded for pedagogical work directly from the budget, i.e. from the Ministry of Education, Science and Sport through the University of Ljubljana. The scientific-research work at BF is funded indirectly through the above-mentioned projects' calls published by the Slovenian Research Agency, which funds basic (including postdoctoral) and applicative research projects and research programmes. Both institutions

are also externally funded by the EU funded projects. Regarding transparency, both institutions are obliged to provide annual reports on their websites.

Regarding the two test departments, the situation is the same as at the organisational level: SSH proved more gender-balanced in its structure (with 5 women Heads of Sections and 1 man Head comparatively through 4 years), but the general structure of employees, which is highly women-dominated should be taken into account. Women are predominant in higher positions, while for the position of young researcher (PhD students) they have equal number of men and women. Technical staff is women-only. For STEM, comparing years from 2010 until 2013, the gender structure of the Chair's Heads did not change (5 men and 1 woman). Gender discrepancy is most visible in the position of Full Professor (men-dominated – 1 male associate professor was promoted to Professor title from 2010-2011) while in the case of the position of Associate Professor the numbers show more a gender-balanced situation. However, this is indicative, since in the case of the positions of Assistant and Assistant with PhD, women are predominant, which proves a glass-ceiling phenomenon that women are less-represented in the highest position. In this regard, it is important to take into account that research positions at the Faculty are usually temporary (temporary contract). According to the interviews, the number of temporary contracts has been increased. In the case of administrative workers and cleaning workers, they are women-only.

From the interviews of key players in both organisations and Departments, gender issues have not been considered as an important aspect of internal policy. In both cases, the emphasis was on the quality of the researcher, either excellence in teamwork and social skills (SSH), or publishing and success in applying for national, or third-party projects from industry (STEM).

Vignette 4: Belgium – Catholic University of Louvain

Belgium- Catholic University of Louvain

Overall Characteristics: “passport” period and “omnipresence”; paradox of “sticky floor” which is teaching vs. focus upon hyper productivity in research, work/life balance more precarious for STEM, parental ambivalence, but once parents also for SSH, however STEM postdocs non-parents, depending on couple also.

Welfare and Gender regimes: Modified male breadwinner model, with female part-time character and unexplained gender pay gap, Federal state.

This macro-sociological analysis has shown us that the gender question remains an open one, even if significant advances towards greater equality are observable. In particular, girls have made the school system their own, especially in terms of levels of studies. They are now in the majority in higher and university education, with higher graduation rates than the boys. Yet two important reservations should be formulated: firstly, access to the highest level of qualification, the doctorate, still remains male in the majority; secondly, a horizontal segmentation between ‘male’ tracks of studies (sciences and technology) and female (human and social sciences) is still reproduced.

The labour market has also been strongly feminized, but here too classical phenomena of horizontal segmentation (between sectors and trades) and vertical (employment and responsibility levels) are present, although they are decreasing. For that matter, an unexplained 10% gender pay gap is still present. One of the important aspects of female employment in Belgium is its part time character. The scale of female part time work should be, at least partially in any case, interpreted as the fruit of work/family conciliation difficulties, expressing the persistence of a sexual and gendered division of work in which an essential part of “care” is still attributed to women. Such a division is also visible in how the time of social activities is distributed between men and women, and within households.

Familial policies supporting work/family conciliation are nevertheless numerous and pursue two logics: a logic of de-commodification notably via measures dealing with working hours (reduction, interruption, leave for family reasons, etc.) and defamilialization measures notably via early childhood care and education, and service-vouchers. These policies undoubtedly support employment rates among women, who are their principal users. They do not however manage to do away with the work/family contradiction, which would moreover seem to imply basically reconsidering the organizing principles of the “labour society” (Fusulier, Nicole-Drancourt, 2015).

On its various levels of power and in its various components, the Belgian State, is sensitized to the question of inequalities between men and women, equality being inscribed into its Constitution. An Institute for the equality of women and men was created a few years ago on the Federal level to continue the struggle against discriminations and promote equality. Intermediate bodies have also been institutionalized and the social partners (employers and trade unions) should introduce this concern on all levels of social consultation (the inter-professional, sectorial and company levels), particularly in order to reduce the “gender pay gap”.

Scientific and academic careers are anchored in this societal configuration. Thus, many women pursue graduate and postgraduate studies but enter a leaky pipeline wherein their downfall may be observed from their doctorate to the highest positions of the statutory hierarchy of university space. The problem of articulating work and family within a gender regime maintaining a sexual division of productive work and reproductive work is one of the apparent causes of this downfall. In addition, a horizontal segmentation is present too, certain scientific disciplines such as the sciences and technology remain male bastions. Incorporating the Helsinki Group’s European recommendations, a political will to counter these phenomena has been making itself felt in the last few years. Today, in the context of applying the European Charter for Researchers (EURAXESS), each French-speaking

university has a person in charge of examining the “gender” issue in producing indicators and formulating proposals for action. A “Women and Sciences” Committee has been inaugurated by the Federation Wallonia-Brussels including representatives of the various universities, the Administration, the Minister in charge of higher education and scientific research as well as the National Fund for Scientific Research. The GARCIA Project consequently works in synergy with these initiatives.

Previous and existing gender policy: No mentoring programmes, some doctoral supports, ongoing and recent discursive gender policy and officer appointment, ongoing with Garcia, but with some institutional resistances.

Quantitative Data: Leaky pipeline, Sticky floor, glass ceiling, postdoc

For the Belgian case, the macro-sociological analysis (WP3, D 3.2) has shown us that the gender question remains an open one, even if significant advances towards greater equality are observable. Although women are now in the majority in higher and university education, with higher graduation rates than the boys, yet two important reservations are still present:

- firstly, access to the highest level of qualification, the obtaining of doctorate, still remains male in the majority;
- secondly, a horizontal segmentation between ‘male’ tracks of studies (sciences and technology) and female (human and social sciences) is still reproduced.

The whole labour market has also been strongly feminized, but here too classical phenomena of horizontal segmentation (between sectors and trades) and vertical (employment and responsibility levels) are present, although they are decreasing. For that matter, an unexplained 10% gender pay gap is still present. One of the important aspects of female employment in Belgium is its part time character. The scale of female part time work can partially be interpreted as the fruit of work/family conciliation difficulties, expressing the persistence of a sexual and gendered division of work in which an essential part of “care” is still attributed to women. Such a division is also visible in how the time of social activities is distributed between men and women, and within households. This kind of data however is not clearly available for the particular case of UCL or the two Garcia institutes. It will be interesting to learn from the qualitative narrative analysis how male and female researchers/academics manage and experience work/life (see WP4/WP6 interview analysis). However, what is notable is that as in the general case for French-speaking Universities, women in academic/scientific careers work more part time than men (13% vs. 6%), but these part time positions are in lower scientific/academic career posts, such as assistants.

☞The higher one climbs the ladder the more full time work in academic careers seems to be a condition. This would perhaps partially explain the lower number of women in professorships and ordinary professorships, and even lesser in decision-making organs and posts.

Familial policies supporting work/family conciliation are nevertheless numerous and pursue two logics: a logic of decommodification via measures dealing with working hours (reduction, interruption, leave for familial reasons, etc.) and defamilialization measures via early childhood care and education, and service-vouchers. If we observe figures of maternity and paternity leaves for the UCL and IACCHOS/ELI in particular, it is noteworthy that not many maternity leaves were taken for the year 2013: 4 women in SSH of which two are each postdocs and assistants and 2 are associate professors/2 in STEM of which 1 is postdoc and other is associate professor. For men, there are 4 paternity leaves taken for STEM, of which all are assistants, in other words ongoing PhDs, and none in SSH. Other types of leaves for family care were taken 2 male and 2 female for STEM and none for SSH. Such familial policies undoubtedly support employment rates among women, who are their principal users. They do not however manage to do away with the work/family contradiction, which would moreover seem to imply basically reconsidering the organizing principles of the wage society (Fusulier, Nicole-Drancourt, 2015). This argument could be supported by the conclusion of D 5.1 for WP5 for Belgium that points to the existence of a particular gender dimension in a professional bureaucracy that can be considered a main organizational logic in UCL, whereby an important glass ceiling is produced. A professional bureaucracy of this kind of constellation can point to an ever increasing workload transferred to individuals, which necessitates high demands of institutional commitment, not only in terms of political or governing involvement of individuals alongside their main work of research and teaching, but also an important increase in logistic, governance and administrative tasks, and of finding own funds, which research centres and faculties are not able to supply in sufficient amounts. There is a form of entrepreneurship (self-regulation and –funding) required on unit- and individual level, without adhering to managerialism. Parallely to this we can count in the effects of the university as a greedy institution (Coser, 1974; Grant et al., 2000; Hendrickson et al., 2011; del Rio Carral, Fusulier, 2013) in that research and teaching demands are today increasing in complexity and availability of the researcher/academic; in 2012 the rector of UCL remarked in the constitution of the university that the researcher/academic needs to be entirely invested in his work. Women (and men) therefore not only have to meet high demands in research/teaching, but in addition also adhere to an important institutional investment and presence in terms of integrating into a hyper-complex system of bureaucracy and institutional culture. Moreover, this type of organization requires a significant actual physical presence of individuals, because decisions are made in meetings, deliberations and through a heady process of negotiation. There seems to be an increasing requirement of « omnipresence » in all three pillars, of which each pillar has increased in levels, demands and complexity of required personal engagement. It can be argued that this can represent important issues to work/life conciliation or balance or having a family life, and that wanting to climb the career ladder also means important choices and pressures in terms of personal life. It is noteworthy that the two highest posts attained by women at UCL today (vice-rector and general administrator), and some other heads of units (presidents of institutes or deans) have profiles of women without children, sometimes not being in a couple. It would be therefore interesting, beyond a mere tracing of glass ceilings and leaky pipelines at UCL to research the type of profiles that women and men in management and other posts have currently, to see whether

certain types emerge as recurrent and more favourable to integration in the local culture and structures of organization, but less favourable to family or private life.

According to the findings in WP3 D 3.1 and 5.1, the problem of articulating work and family within a gender regime maintaining a sexual division of productive work and reproductive work is one of the apparent causes of this downfall. In addition, a horizontal segmentation is present too, certain scientific disciplines such as the sciences and technology remain male bastions.

In terms of the models of scientific/academic career and the pathways of progression or climbing the ladder, the nature of how recruitment works (see D 7.1) and the organizational culture point to an importance of the informal nature of dealings, interactions and local ways of integration into the system (see also above WPS D 5.1). Firstly, for the primary stages of the career, doctoral and postdoctoral funding in French-speaking Belgian universities is largely dependent on external subsidies or funding bodies, such as the FNRS (National Foundation of Research and Science) or the EC. Some limited funds are supported by industrial sectors. There is also some PhD research funded by governmental foundations (Roi Boudouin, Belspo). All these funding paths are however subject to a very harsh, and what can increasingly be gleaned for the case of the FNRS, very political selection and appointment of a massive increase in candidates (especially international or external candidates to the given university, which is hardly surprising if we consider the international mobility and attractiveness discourse running in university policy lately, see WP 5.1). However, the large numbers of ongoing PhDs, both male and female point to multiple possibilities existent. Obtaining PhDs is a grey zone upon which we do not have much data apart from the CDH study data. There is an ongoing study about motivation and abandonment of PhDs conducted currently at UCL by a group of psychology researchers with whom we have some collaborative interactions. It will be interesting to have their large-scale quantitative and qualitative data on how PhD's feel in terms of completing and advancing in their doctorates.

There is then after obtaining PhD and postdoctoral contracts, an important hurdle to overcome for young researchers to obtain or gain admission/nomination into permanent lectureship posts, which is the most common academic career path. Another pathway is through the appointment of a permanent FNRS researcher, affiliated to a particular university. However, this pathway too is very competitive and political often in nature. For the recruitment into academic posts, the figures at UCL point to as many female researchers being actually recruited as there are female candidates for the post (see D 7.1). However, at a closer look, the recruitment process is split into multiple complex segments: first there is a selection of "dossiers" of candidates (of which there are still many for very few openings per year or two/three year) based on competitive criteria (see 7.1 report for Belgium) such as publications, types of projects obtained, CV, place of education and PhD, mobility etc. Then upon closer selection, three or four candidates are retained for a three-fold interviewing and self-presentation recruitment process, in which recruitment committees (with very different dynamics and presidents) negotiate the "ideal candidate" for what is often a very local nomination, defending the interests of being able to integrate/fit and collaborate with existing teams, and being able to ensure the handling of and carrying out what are deemed all three (or four) pillars of academic work (research production, teaching, institutional engagement and perhaps also contribution to society). Qualitative and policy findings point to a recruitment and scientific/academic career model which favours general or competitive criteria and focus upon high production of research and research-orientated skills in the early stages of the career ladder (Masters, doctorate, postdoc), and a sudden expected leap into local integration and juggling multiple academic spheres, of which the institutional and self-administering engagement level becomes higher the higher the post. If we consider the age groups of persons entering and progressing (or not) up the career ladder then it cannot be disputed that this is between early twenties and late thirties for doctoral and postdoctoral levels, which are arguably family forming or settling more firmly into adulthood from a social point of view. The gender dimension therefore may play a more significant role as to how much women and men are willing to invest, to engage in and what they can actually perform in terms of work, production, engagement etc., and how open or closed the organizational culture and structures (both of which is created by all actors in the organization) are towards these performances, these work/life articulations and whether integration of either are at order.

Incorporating the Helsinki Group's European recommendations, some limited political will to counter these phenomena has been making itself felt in the last few years. Today, in the context of applying the European Charter for Researchers (EURAXESS), each French-speaking university has appointed a person in charge of examining the "gender" issue in producing indicators and formulating proposals for action. A "Women and Sciences" Committee has been inaugurated by the Walloon- Brussels Federation including representatives of the various universities, the Administration, the Minister in charge of higher education and scientific research as well as the National Fund for Scientific Research. Within the GARCIA Project, we are trying to work in synergy with these initiatives, but are encountering nonetheless some resistances in local policy makers about its action-orientated nature and intervening character.

Qualitative Results:

Postdocs:

- "passport" period problematic, because it presents an ambivalent rapport to work and the profession due to precariousness, pressures and tensions: Male and female interviewees in all groups describe and make sense of in terms of a career: demonstrate and justify a consistency and productivity of their intellectual development over time. In this process there are multiple barriers and hurdles to cross before being able to build a sufficiently "important" CV to be even considered for a permanent position: rarely question as being important career strategies, such as being mobile, publishing, building the CV, having career advice from mentors, collaborating to build research projects and moving towards advancing into a permanent position.

On the whole, a picture emerges of a period of professional struggle, and tensions with family building.

- Parenthood tipping scale towards ambivalence: while female and male childless postdocs are engaged and optimistic about their work level, intensity and male and female postdocs with children are more ambivalent about work and family.

Newly Tenured: SSH parenthood tipping scale towards ambivalence, omnipresence :

Moreover, the newly tenured males and females tip the scale of being optimistic toward being ambivalent by having children. However, there is a clear gender difference in the way this ambivalence is experienced: females have more ambivalence in the question about compatibility of children with career, more feelings of guilt for 8me away from children, and also speak about health reasons, overwork and infringement upon or sacrifice of family, mobility and leaving the country due to career choices.

- Omnipresence and “blurry” or double edged flexibility: A significant result is that interviewees speak about the importance of having the multiple pillars of academia/research, as it offers a balance between research, teaching and collaboration, but male and also female newly tenured express the frustration of “omnipresence”, which extends work towards multiple pillars in what is a very “blurry” through flexible time/space profession (research, teaching, institutional engagement, community service).

- Moreover, there is a constant bid for funding that is lacking, a constant justification of research, which shifts the focus away from actual research and academic work.

- Paradox about the nature of the “sticky floor” itself that is the teaching task. Teaching has become undervalued and devalued in

scientific/academic field, whereby competition-based recruitment criteria put all the emphasis on research development and production (publications, mobility, bidding for funds) and early researchers account for trying to meet with these criteria for career progression and obtaining permanent posts.

Movers/Leavers:

Leavers: Better job satisfaction, not wanting to subscribe to competitive anti-social culture, more women declaring some regret, incompatibility with parenthood

Movers: Relief at having achieved, but women struggling as newly tenured with ambivalence upon parenthood and work/life balance issues, omnipresence

Recruitment and discursive resources:

The joint vision upon the contents of the job descriptions, the HR documents provided by the rector’s office in UCL, the different groups of interviews and the focus group, along with linking all these results with other WPs, provide a very rich picture of different dimensions of organizational logics and extra-organizational logics at play before, during and beyond recruitment processes. What emerges for the case of UCL and the two institutes in question, IACCHOS and ELI, is that there is a kind of overarching tension that confronts criteria and demands of young candidates in recruitment processes of D- and C-level posts that are more general and what can be called de-localized, international or competition-based criteria and more local, institutional and nomination-based requirements. On the one hand, what becomes visible in both the job descriptions, criteria described and circulated in HR documents and interviewees experiences of criteria in their committees is a rising importance of what is called scientific “excellence” or “experience”, which is equalled to production of research, made visible and validated through publications. These publications, on the local practical reality of committee recruitment processes of selection, are not required to be long lists.

However, the legitimization and validation of publications and of candidates’ research is required to happen through international approbation. Peer review in internationally renowned journals is something that is accepted and recognized by most if not all interviewees as something indispensable for candidates’ dossiers these days, and for what can be called a good “quality” of the research carried out. We would argue in line with Brink and Benschop (2014) that this is highly dependent upon the possibilities of building social networks for the candidates in question and their social capital. The impact factor indicators or other indicators are seen to be not entirely reliable in measuring quality, but are nonetheless accepted as a measure becoming more common in various fields, as much in SSH as in STEM fields. This reflects the discursive subscription of our case study university to the global emphasis on excellence through internationalization and new managerialism. International mobility is something that without exception was seen as something essential in the formation process of becoming a good researcher, of having seen other research contexts, of having acquired international contacts and colleagues abroad. Thus one could say that the competition-based criteria have gained some ground in both fields in the experience of committee member academics in recruitment processes today, at least on the level of the intimal selection and filtering of applications in the process. Moreover, these more competition-based criteria are named and seen as being important changes in the recruitment process in what was seen as a more non-biased, non-subjective and open recruitment, in terms of competition, rather than nomination or appointment. The higher instance interviewees in key positions moreover spoke of the opening of scientific and academic jobs to the international market. We could speak about the introduction of new regulation logics productivity, competitiveness, accountability and mobility. There is therefore the idea of a market logic that has entered the university institution, but seen as something favourable to ensuring equity and non-discrimination.

However, upon more detailed questioning of interviewees, what becomes perceivable is that this very focus upon competition-based criteria (publication, mobility, networking) could in itself be discriminate, as the criteria are applied in a non-differentiated way to all applicants and candidates, without taking into account “gaps” in careers often non-declared in CVs, or in terms of what the job actually required at appointment. The requirements and criteria pre-require a certain type of profile, somebody who would have had the necessary time and personal

situation to publish, to travel etc. In this sense, the type of profile could be subscribed to by women (or men) or not; the question was raised whether this kind of profile was something many women could imagine being or working to the detriment of family life and situations, or whether they would rather deviate to other career paths in the first place, already before recruitment. Often, interviewees would speak about how women candidates arriving at the final stage of selection would have a certain type of profile that “fits” with the requirement model of the scientific excellent candidate; bachelor, non-committed, ready to relocate, to adapt, etc. One could draw a first conclusion that the scientific profile in the general criteria highlighted in both SSH and STEM institutes, perhaps more so in SSH, is orientated around mobile researchers, and de-localized criteria.

If we now put this in comparison with the other criteria named by most if not all interviewees and focus group discussants, is what they sees as the vital importance of institutional engagement, service to the institutional, rootedness, organizational logics and knowledge thereof, the evaluation of the potential of the candidate to “fit” and to articulate with the institutional context and its research and teaching context, the emphasis on teaching capacity in the case of SSH and willingness to teach in STEM, then we could call these criteria more local, informal and nomination-based. Brink and Benschop (2014) have pointed out how gatekeepers legitimize preferences on the nomination level with quality or excellence, but that in fact jobs are offered to those who are suitable and not necessarily excellent. These nomination criteria are less highlighted in the initial job descriptions and HR documents, although they are enlisted, sometimes even in first place before scientific experience or excellence. However, according to the criteria named by interviewees, teaching and institutional engagement come after scientific excellence, and become important decisive criteria only in the final short-listed selection of three to four candidates in C-level appointment. Along with this, there is a whole narrative focus upon organizational logics, the power dynamics between committee members and other hierarchical instances. All these factors point to the “local” dimension, which is very strong in the sense that candidates are seen to require this organizational knowledge, rootedness, a teaching culture and collaborative ways or working that go far beyond the mere scientific logic of the initially named criteria. The potential of the person to “fit in” and to become a member of this internal and local logic and “elite” is not something given to all candidates, especially when looking at all the emphasis of requirements of scientific excellence defined as “internationally legitimized and validated” (peer reviewed publications in international journals, international mobility, networks and research project work); many interviewees acknowledge that internal candidates are easier to evaluate in the sense of knowing whether they would “fit” because they are already there. Whereas, external candidates, despite scientific excellence in most cases, are more “risky” in the local sense; will they “fit”, will they “stay”, do they have “local interests at heart and mind” are all concerns voiced about candidates that are not necessarily only externals, but also research types, who are considered individualists, ego-centric etc., and a menace to the local work organization. This kind of risk- and trust-based gatekeeping practices could therefore enhance gender inequality, because of networking preferences; men identifying with the similar, already present male researchers, who are their mentees or affiliated researchers or known to them through the internal network. Or men and women subscribing to the proven success model that has masculine orientations to work ethic or requirements (Acker, 1990; van den Brink and Benschop, 2014).

There seem to be multiple ambiguities or tensions that can be named with respect to this opposition between the competition-based criteria and logic of recruitment and the nomination-based logic. Firstly the difference between the focus of requirements of the scientific career in its early stages, as of the PhD, which is clearly connected with demands and requirements of scientific or research orientation; developing ones’ research, consolidating it and validating this in visible publications. The postdoctoral criteria affirm this research profile, by the project type work and its particularities (time frame, work load, leadership, coordination, independence, innovation etc.) and the criteria named by that group of interviewees. The final selection criteria are however much more academic, simply because finally the recruitment of C-level posts are “academic” posts and not research posts. Ensuring teaching, ensuring institutional engagement become key criteria for an academic appointment. The scientific factor or excellence shifts therefore into the background, and in fact is sometimes penalized as a too “individualist” or ego-centric “star” logic, which cannot function as a sole criterion. So there is a problem of making and promoting scientists through the scientific excellence criteria gaining ground in institutions, and then requiring academics, who finally have very different qualities and require certain very local ways of being. This becomes visible when interviewees speak about having made “mistakes” in recruiting excellent researchers, who however could not fulfil the academic teaching mandate, because they simply did not like teaching and did not have rapports with the students. And others who wanted to be left in peace for doing research. This becomes further visible in the description of the tool PAIC, which is supposed to assist newly appointed academics, but which ends up being an additional pressure to ensure teaching as well as research.

Another tension is in the form of recruitment processes itself, in that the local organizational logics and dynamics that exist and operate within the centres, institutes and UCL itself plays out in the committee, through the processes of negotiating the ideal candidate that “fits” and “suits” the gatekeepers, of self-preserving and assessing the “risky” and “trustworthy” or “safe” candidates, of hierarchical and “tribal” power dynamics finally have as much of an impact on recruitment decisions, as much as initial criteria of scientific excellence; the initial filtering is perhaps done according to the these general criteria, which are supposed to open the competition and ensure a non-biased process; however, the final decisions are very local. We would argue moreover that the competition-based criteria are in no way neutral or based upon meritocracy as the discourse in universities likes to claim; they are linked to intricate play of social networks to which one has or has not access. There is also the discussion that recruitment processes are long and arduous, and begin at planning periods within faculties, and extend beyond nomination through the hard process of probation of three years before becoming a permanent employee. There is a tension between ways of operating between different stages of the recruitment process that are somewhat de-coupled, and the continual struggle of affirmation and validation of candidates throughout the entire process.

Finally, the gender dimension aspects emerging from the document and interview/focus group material from these opposing logics described above, are likely to contribute to the subscription or not of women and men to playing

the game, or of gaining membership to the elite of academia. The period of recruitment has to be extended to much before the actual recruitment, in the sense of how easy or difficult it is for persons (of either sex) of entering into these existing often opposing logics of competing demands, and are they willing to do so. The low turnout of women may perhaps partially apply to this conflict. There is also the interesting figures in UCL that the turnout of women in recruitment processes and the percentage engaged are very close, therefore throwing doubts about the discrimination potential of recruitment processes. Another question to be asked is whether, having gone through the selection and being chosen, do they “survive” and persist in this logic, and what does this do to their work and personal experience, and quality and balancing of different aspects of life.

Organisational features/modalities: closed envelope funding, bid for funding by government through increasing student numbers, faculties have different allocation, whereby STEM three times more than SSH per student rata. Professional Bureaucracy, with administration catering strongly to central governance and less to teaching and research units, self-governance and self-management, auto-managers, competition.

In terms of the different sections of this report, the managerial Framework points to a circular or multi-governing system or organization within the UCL. The different governing organs have a cross-referencing and cross-intervening power in terms of decision-making in general management; such as defining tasks and functions, setting research or teaching programs. However, it is noteworthy that the members of the direction (rector, vice-rectors and general administrator) are omnipresent in all governing organs and therefore have a lot of power in the different negotiation processes that take place in the different councils (scientific, academic and administrative) for all university concerns, including the articulation of research and teaching frameworks, budgeting and financial management. Negotiation, debating, deliberation are recurrent notions or concepts that appear in nearly all descriptions, codes and regulations of university governance at all levels, especially in the governing organs and councils. There is moreover a discourse emerging in interviews about certain ways of doing things in a kind of UCL governing culture; concepts such as humanism and Christian foundations emerge in historical and narrative descriptions. “Avoiding conflict”, indirect and roundabout governing, keeping silent rather than voicing can push through certain decisions in favour of stronger and more opinionated personas or group of persons, such as for example in recruitment or nomination processes of academic staff. There is an important number of commissions, committees and services in aid of decision-making authorities and councils: an idea of knowledge-and deliberation based decision-making springs to mind. These commissions, committees and services moreover have more significant numbers of female as well as male members from different sectors, externals or syndicates.

Although the Councils have representative members of the scientific and academic personnel and the different sectors, there is a definitely male dominated governance on all university concerns, except perhaps for the protection and prevention at work commissions and for the council of enterprise that is concerned with employee as well as employer interests. Otherwise, the percentage of women in the governing bodies does not exceed 20% for the general decision-making and 10% for the Institute level of governance. This becomes quite significant if we consider the functions of the different heads of sectors (deans, vice-deans), the vice-rectors responsible for the sectors (of the six of which one female) and the presidents of institutes (two of 21). The first are key in setting the research, teaching and administrative frameworks of the three sectors (SSH, SSS, STEM), the second act as arbitrators in the case of conflicts and in the regulation or smooth running of sectors and the latter are significant in the managing of the careers and personal development of academic and scientific staff of their institutes. However, there is amongst the direction heads, such as the (female) vice-rector of politics of personnel the idea that having more women in management does not necessarily resolve or improve situations or conditions for women in scientific/academic careers. The discourse runs more in the direction of the ‘nature of scientific/academic work’, the individual capacities to meet with the challenges of the career, which are often described as ‘being what they are’ and ‘having high demands’, which seems conform to the supposed ideas or *illusio* of the profession.

For all that is Human Resource management many different services with a significant number of administrative and technical personnel, of which around 85% is female, is allocated and under the regulation by the governing organs. The Financial management is quite stringently governed with one main head, whose office is now renewed for further four years, with a distinct order of budgeting on the level of the whole university. Many calculations of financial budget are based upon precedence or previous year calculations and therefore have little changes programmed, so we can speak about a path dependency effect. However, once the budgets are distributed to the three sectors, the vice-rector of the sectors and sub-heads (Deans and vice-deans) and faculties seem to have some freedom as to how they allocate their budget within their units. However, what becomes clear is that there must exist a vast difference in the governing of budgets according to the sectors, given that the student pro-rata differs vastly between the three sectors, with SST getting the most student pro-rata budget, then SSS and lastly SSH. Both in research and in teaching the governing units are orientated towards becoming entrepreneurs or business units, which need to manage their own affairs, and increasingly get their own funds. Moreover, the “closed envelope” policy of financing received from public authorities puts universities into an invisible competition. There is also a great reliance on funding acquired by the personnel themselves, which makes up an important amount of UCL Financial resource for sustaining the localities, infrastructure etc. In terms of European large scale funded and nationally funded projects, there is a clear upper hand of male academics (professors and associate professors), who obtain these types of projects in both SSH/IACCHOS and less so in STEM/ELI for national projects. This difference in numbers is more striking in STEM. In terms of discerning the gender dimension in budgeting it is not easy to glean much information from the data we have managed to acquire or which were available to us. The discourse implies that the gender dimension is not taken much into consideration for budgeting plans.

On the policy level there is a coherence of discourses or ideas/images that emerge throughout the documents analysed and also the interviews held with key governing actors. There is an emphasis on the following aspirations: The need for international visibility/Facilitating UCL’s access to the great European or international networks of research / reinforcing their engagement in the three missions of the university; teaching, research and service to

society/openness to internal, external and international recruitment/ increasing UCL as an international employer/ reinforcing the pedagogical traditions and ensuring that the student is at the centre of his formation; this is seen to be achieved with ICT (Information, Communication and Technology)/ deliberately situating UCL in a new European space of higher Education/ multi-site and collaborative character of university and direct networking of multiple teams in different regional institutions/fortifying the French-speaking Wallonia-Brussels/ multiplying the possibilities of interdisciplinary work/interdisciplinary institutes IACCHOS and ELI/ presence of foreign researchers (doctorates and post-doctorates), to contribute in a wider range of researchers and to attract students/ increasing investment (social, cultural, political and economic)/ Increasing external partners : political and economic. On the Gender and equality level: Gender dimension : individual conditions, situations and will of academics/scientifics women and men matter, nature of work matters rather than bias or discrimination per se in governance: structures are not at fault/ Gender equality : Action program without action so far, but rather mapping tasks/ Protection and prevention at work/ Work time balance.

On the institute level: Interdisciplinary research and collaboration/ International and European funding/Local embeddedness and regional engagement/ Sustainable development and change/ Understanding complexity in society and natural and technical environment/ Gender: work/life balance/ Good academic: three pillars/missions of university (research, teaching, university engagement)/ Service to society/ Increased needs for individual funds

In terms of administration, organizing and HR services: reinforcing professionalization, a harmonization of practices, a coherence of the whole and a dynamic of sharing knowledge and experiences, providing support to the central management for decision-making

In terms of budgeting or financial management: closed envelop and competition between institutions, attractiveness to students/attracting students, autonomy of sectors and institutes, spin-off firms, no mention of gender dimension.

If we take into account the discursive ideas and orientations that emerge in both policy documents as well as interview material, and take into account the structural forms of governing, both on formal and informal levels, then a picture emerges of the UCL as an organization that may be described as a classic professional bureaucracy, as could be referred to by Mintzberg (1982) in his model of structures and dynamics of organizations. He models the different types of organizational structures according to what he sees is the primary problem undertaken by organizations of organizing work. For UCL, what can be remarked is a complexity of structure with many layers and interactions of parallel hierarchical levels of governance, with three different thematic strands of governance, which are teaching, research and technical and administrative management. There is an emphasis on precedence and path dependency. There is moreover a more formalized management process and a more informal management process, which emerges in a kind of local culture of negotiation, deliberation and cross-referencing of all governing units, and the research and academic individuals within this hyper-complex system. This also means an increase in meetings, council deliberations that one has to attend in order to « stay in the game ». The professional bureaucratic structure shows 1) a centralization on the level of support of administrative and technical services in favour of the central management. The policies and structures show that at UCL the logistic support is increasingly centralized to cater to the strategic summit, in other words to central management. Services, commissions and HR that aid central management decision-making. At the same time, there is 2) a de-centralization of logistic support toward the two pillars of the hierarchical line, research and teaching. This means that increasingly institutes, centres, faculties and schools have less logistic personnel, infrastructure and financial resources for their logistics in their units, and the individuals in the operational centre, the academics and researchers, have less financial resources at their disposal for logistics and for research and teaching. The other side of this coin is that they are given a relative autonomy in the structuring of research or teaching and of managing their resources and of governing their own units. Within this kind of schema however, the outcome of this is that 3) increasingly the individuals have to cater for themselves in this complex bureaucratic system, as much operating in an informal and negotiating way, in order to A) manage and administer to their work and B) in order to advance in their careers. An important aspect for both A) and B) for individuals is therefore to cope with additional work apart from the high demands of research production/publication/collaboration, of teaching, and of also managing technically and administratively their own work. They need to know how things are done, but more importantly they need to know persons who are capable of helping them either in terms of career advancement, or of supplying logistics for your work. There is therefore a significance of the creation of networks and of groups of persons in your environment available to you, to which you can apply to. Moreover, often at UCL, application for things is done in multiple pathways; you can apply for either logistics, conflict resolution or for career advancement by going upwards unit by unit through the hierarchical line, or often people skip hierarchical units and apply for concerns directly to vice-rectors (perhaps in favour of your disciplinary or personal cause) or to general administrators and rectors. So there is a culture of hierarchical equality; whilst maintaining a simultaneous reverent respect for current governing authorities; a consensus by keeping quiet or an opposition by applying quietly to other governing units; by negotiating processes. These ways of organizing work could lean upon the historical Christian and Humanistic precepts of UCL. Individual actors also speak about a conflict-avoiding or indirect culture; often demands or claims are not favourably looked upon if too direct. Respectively the Syndicates have a rather weaker power in the organigram. The three corps usually apply to and defend their own group interests (researchers, academics and admin and technical staff) and do not link causes.

If we analyse the gender dimension in a professional bureaucracy, it can be clearly said that there is an important glass ceiling existing at UCL. A professional bureaucracy of this kind of constellation can point to an ever increasing workload transferred to individuals, which necessitates high demands of institutional engagement, not only in terms of political or governing involvement of individuals alongside their main work of research and teaching, but also an important increase in logistic, governance and administrative tasks, and of finding own funds, which research centres and faculties are not able to supply in sufficient amounts. There is a form of entrepreneurship

required on unit-and individual level, without adhering to managerialism. Parallely to this we can count in the effects of the university as a greedy institution (Coser, 1974; Grant et al., 2000; Hendrickson et al., 2011; del Rio Carral, Fusulier, 2013) in that research and teaching demands are today increasing in complexity and availability of the researcher/academic; in 2012 the rector of UCL remarked in the constitution of the university that the researcher/academic needs to be entirely invested in his work. Women (and men) therefore not only have to meet high demands in research/teaching, but in addition also adhere to an important institutional investment and presence in terms of integrating into a hyper-complex system of bureaucracy and institutional culture. Moreover, this type of organization requires a significant actual physical presence of individuals, because decisions are made in meetings, deliberations and through a heady process of negotiation. There seems to be an increasing requirement of « omnipresence » in all three pillars, of which each pillar has increased in levels, demands and complexity of required personal engagement. It can be argued that this can represent important issues to work/life conciliation or balance or having a family life, and that wanting to climb the career ladder also means important choices and pressures in terms of personal life. It is noteworthy that the two highest posts attained by women at UCL today (vice-rector and general administrator), and some other heads of units (presidents of institutes or deans) have profiles of women without children, sometimes not being in a couple. It would be therefore interesting, beyond a mere tracing of glass ceilings and leaky pipelines at UCL to research the type of profiles that women and men in management and other posts have currently, to see whether certain types emerge as recurrent and more favourable to integration in the local culture and structures of organization, but less favourable to family or private life.

Vignette 5: The Netherlands – Radboud University

The Netherlands-Radboud University

Overall Characteristics: Key moments different between “career” and “life”, pressures that make people cope with or not, leave or stay, Motherhood/foreignhood

Gender and Welfare regimes: Foreign and “local” or nationals regimes and labour regimes, modified breadwinner

In this report, we have evaluated the societal and institutional Dutch context for the domains education, employment, family formation and work-life issues in order to be able to define elements that structure the career opportunities for women and men in the early stages of their academic careers. Next, we discussed policies introduced by the government in general and in the academic sector specifically that aim to come to a more gender equal situation in society at large, and in academia. Women’s level of education has improved significantly over the years. In general, women nowadays are highly educated. More women than men have tertiary qualifications. At the doctoral level, only one third of all doctorate holders are women. However, when we consider the young generation, the number of women with a PhD is much higher. When we zoom in on the different fields of studies at the tertiary level, we find persisting sex segregation. Particularly, the underrepresentation of women in Science – both in historical and cross-national perspective – is extreme. In the domain of employment, this same pattern of both horizontal and vertical segregation is reproduced. Women tend to work in particular sectors, and are underrepresented in top positions. We find the same tendency in the academic sector. Despite the high number of women students and growing number of female PhD candidates and their good performance, women in academia are especially underrepresented at the level of assistant, associate and full professors. Since 1980 we see an improvement, but the phenomenon of the ‘leaky pipeline’ still applies very well to the Dutch situation: the higher the rank, the less women we find. Women are also underrepresented in university boards. Currently, a high percentage of women in the Netherlands is participating on the labour market, yet most of them are in part-time jobs. The Netherlands can be best characterized as a one-and-a-half earner model: the most dominant working arrangement of (heterosexual) couples in the Netherlands is a situation in which the man has a full-time job, and the woman a part-time job. This situation is more often true when couples have children. While part-time work is a key characteristic for the Dutch labour market, women with a university degree tend to work much more often in full-time jobs. The same goes for women working in the academic sector. Yet, female assistant and associate professors much less often work in full-time positions than their male colleagues. At the same time, the gender difference for full-time jobs is small at the level of full professorship. This means that especially at the start of their careers women work less working hours. Besides, the recent and sharp increase in temporary contracts in the academic sector particularly affects the job security of women as they more often than men work on temporary contracts.

The policies and practices around care and work-life issues remain rather traditional in the Dutch context. The impact of child-birth affects women more than men. Even though the number of women that reduce their working hours after child-birth is still high, women nowadays tend to do this less often than before. Compared to men, women are still primarily responsible for and spend more time on childcare and domestic work. Despite a culture of taking care of children in the family (by the mother), the use of formal childcare has increased rapidly.

Besides equal treatment laws, gender equality policy measures in the Netherlands are primarily soft policies. Emancipation policy continues to focus on women’s labour market participation and women’s economic independence. Measures taken often intend to improve the representation of women in organisations. Politically, there is resistance to the more radical measure to improve the underrepresentation of women by compulsory

quotas and therefore target figures are preferred. To conclude, measures mainly focus on increasing numbers, and less on more structural changes.

With regard to the academic sector, both the government and universities themselves have been actively introducing individual and structural measures to improve the situation of women. Unfortunately, there is a general lack of monitoring and evaluation of these policies and their effectiveness (van den Brink 2010: 61). Research on the Dutch academic sector does show that measures are not fully applied everywhere, and success depends on committed initiators (ibid.).

Previous and existing gender policy: Strong, peer mentoring programmes and woman's promoting programme with merits or points systems, supportive of Garcia research project; excellence, coaching of champions (female also

Quantitative Data: Leaky pipeline, glass ceiling, bottleneck

We see that in internationally comparison (OECD, EU), the Netherlands has one of the lowest numbers of women full professors. In both the STEM and the SSH field, on both the national and the organizational level, the leaky pipeline is present. The numbers and percentages of women on academic positions differ between the STEM and the SSH domain, on both the national and the organizational level, but the trend of decreasing numbers at every step in the pipeline is present everywhere. Yet, in both participating GARCIA departments in the Netherlands, the IMAPP (STEM) and the IMR (SSH), we see higher percentages of women full professors than women associate professors. The number of women full professors is higher than the national average in the IMR, but lower in the IMAPP. In both the IMAPP and the IMR we found an increasing number of women non-tenured staff over the years 2010-2014, however no increase in the number of women tenured staff. This indicates an increasing leak in the pipeline at the assistant professor level in the IMAPP and IMR. In the IMAPP, the number of women staff leaving seems to be disproportionate, when compared to the number of women employed. This is not the case within the IMR.

Despite the similarity of the career ladder in the IMAPP and the IMR (PhD – postdoc – assistant prof – associate prof – full prof), the criteria for the positions differ, particularly at the early stages of the academic career. Earning a Veni or Vidi grant is a great stimulant for the career prospects of early career researchers within the Netherlands, however only attainable for very few academics. Within the IMAPP, getting a Veni or Vidi is almost a requirement to get hired or to get tenure, whereas in the IMR it is more of a bonus and more exceptional when a staff member receives such a grant.

In general, the Netherlands has the highest number of women working part-time and a one-and-a-half earners model is prevalent. Care divisions between men and women are still conservative. However, the prevalence of part-time work does not apply to women in academia. Previous research in the University of Tilburg has shown that fathers and mothers in academia hardly differ in their contract hours (Van Engen et al., 2008), which was confirmed by a research project in Delft (Van Engen, Bleijenbergh, Vinkenburg, 2010). In Delft, only at the assistant professor level women worked slightly fewer hours than men. The research project in Tilburg also showed that women academics have more often no children or fewer children than women outside academia. A pay gap exists between men and women with tertiary education.

Qualitative Results:

Postdocs:

Networking/being sponsored: Within the IMR, the Institute for Management Research (SSH), the flowing postdoc and doubting postdoc had been sponsored by senior academics to come to the IMR and do research there. The first had also been stimulated and encouraged by former supervisors to enter and stay in academia. Within the IMAPP, the Institute for Mathematics, Astrophysics, and Particle Physics (STEM) postdocs were quite aware of the relevance of networking and people were more strategic in building networks.

- Applying for grants: In the IMAPP more than in the IMR, postdocs were geared towards writing research proposals and gaining (prestigious) research grants. The first reason was to be able to conduct (their own) research, and the second reason was that acquiring grants would increase their chances of gaining a higher or permanent position at a later stage in their career. Writing grants did eat up their time, which they could not use for paper writing.

- Acting pro-actively/strategically: In the sample of postdocs we see a gradation of postdocs going from talking about a chance to do research but being not really ambitious to talking about making sacrifices for their passion for science. These sacrifices go from health (multiple illnesses reported) to relationships, to building a family. What is remarkable is that some postdocs mentioned not to invest much in their present institute as they would leave after a while, but focus on their own publications and grants. This is directly impacted by the academic norm of mobility and short term contracts. The other side of the coin is that several postdocs, especially the women within IMR, mentioned feeling isolated. IMAPP seemed to have a more social climate than IMR. Possibly, the lack of experience with postdocs within IMR limited the available (formal or informal) supporting infrastructure for postdocs. This could make postdocs in the IMR even more responsible for their own wellbeing than within IMAPP, where postdocs are well embedded in academic careers and a social and supportive infrastructure.

- Being flexible: Like for the flowing movers, flexibility was key in the group of postdocs. Flexibility in terms of moving abroad, but also in terms of combining a career with other responsibilities. We noted this especially in the IMAPP. The majority of postdocs had a partner, and different arrangements were made regarding living together or apart and moving abroad together (or not). The two body problem with regard to academic partners was mentioned by several women postdocs from the IMAPP. Postdocs were seen as part of the standard route of an academic career by IMAPP postdocs. This was not the case within IMR.

- Balance research and education: The focus of the postdocs, both in the IMAPP and IMR, was predominantly on doing research. In IMAPP this was preferably independent research based on a personal grant. Especially in the IMAPP, postdocs were more aimed at publishing than the assistant professors (see next section). Teaching was seen by some postdocs as an obligation, by others as a necessity, and if done, it was on their own initiative and preferably related to their own research.

Tenure-track assistant professors: While all current SSH interviewees were parents as many as 4 out of 9 current STEM interviewees did not have any children. This was also the case for postdocs. This could be an indication that the emphasis on masculine habitus is stronger in STEM fields. STEM fields are strongly masculinised and are generally rewarded more funding and have more prestige linked to them.

Teaching is a requirement for assistant professors in both the IMR and the IMAPP. For starting assistant professors, this usually takes up a lot of time, as they have to get acquainted with the curriculum.

Research; publications, projects; Balance research and education: For all interviewees, balancing research and education and extra tasks was an issue. Juggling with many different tasks was a challenge. We did see that among the IMR interviewees teaching and gaining Teaching Qualifications were discussed more than by the IMAPP assistant professors. Publications were the next important issue for IMR interviewees after grants. The IMAPP interviewees on the other hand gave the impression that acquiring grant funding was more important for one's career than publishing. This is most likely because acquiring grant funding is a criterion for getting tenure. Furthermore, IMAPP interviewees already had longer career trajectories than the IMR interviewees and had hence already published more and proved themselves as researcher, which could increase their chances of getting grants.

- Flexibility also meant being flexible with one's time schedule. The norm of working more than full-time was implicit in many accounts: This notion of 'self-driven' work was present among many assistant professors. This left interviewees with a certain freedom to arrange for their own time spending and career planning, but also put the responsibility for guarding their time, achievements and prospects on them. This is an issue that resounds throughout all interviewee samples. Science was called 'a hobby' or something similar by many interviewees in all interviewee groups, both flowers and hangers – though doubters less – and something they enjoyed dedicating their life to.

- Mobility or living abroad; experienced as habitual practice during postdoc: passage point.

Movers/leavers:

While all current SSH academics interviewees were parents as many as 4 out of 9 current STEM academics did not have any children. This could be an indication that the emphasis on masculine habitus is stronger in STEM fields. STEM fields are strongly masculinised and are generally rewarded more funding and have more prestige linked to them.

- Teaching is built, and takes up a lot of time. It is also perceived a necessary step for assistant professors for salary raises and promotions.

- Mobility or living abroad; experienced as habitual practice during postdoc: passage point

- Leavers reasons: being academic as a lonely 'hero' with all requirements, among which there is an increasing need for grants and funding; the existence of 'old boys networks', a need for networks and sponsors, a need for support within institute in getting position or grant; the existence of a precarity loop; the difficulty of balancing between teaching and education. On the individual level, motherhood is a key issue in terms of work-life balance, having children or not, especially for women (part-time working culture); a willingness to juggle work-life balance and tolerate stress; the partner's presence; the foreign effect, going abroad and mobility, being Dutch or foreign; a 'passion' for the job

- Networking and/or being sponsored were elements in most of the movers' stories. From multiple interviews, conferences appeared as an important platform for job hunting.

- The mover careers also often included an (extended) period of (extensive) applying for grants and jobs.

Being flexible was an aspect that was often implicitly present in the stories, but sometimes also made explicit by the interviewee. Moving institutes, changing countries, and dealing flexibly with partners and family are indicative of this element. For instance, these movers were willing to have a long distance relationship with an (academic) partner or move their family abroad.

The movers were constantly seeking to balance research and education: A difference we noted between the men and women flowing movers regarding the trajectories was in the self-positioning during the interviews. Several of the men were explicitly positioning themselves as confident, flexible and autonomous academics.

The image the leavers had of the academic system was one of fierce competition and politics in which the 'ideal academic' participated in image building and emphasized publishing over more practical impact. The lack of a sponsor was paramount to several interviewees leaving academia. Both men and women had left academia.

Hanging movers: The academic system seems to demand these competition-based aspects of individuals for them to succeed, which apparently is harder for women when combining these with caring responsibilities. The system had driven these women to leave the 'mainstream' academic track and find jobs on side tracks (i.e., a non-academic part-time job, and online lecturing) to find job security (IMR) and have a paid academic job (IMAPP).

- In the analysis of the flowing movers we saw that most of them were non-Dutch, had moved abroad after their IMAPP/IMR employment, and had found (semi-)permanent jobs. Implicitly and explicitly, the interviewees showed

that moving abroad was part of the job. Leaving academia was not an option for any of the flowing movers. What was noticeable is how all flowing IMAPP movers had children, whereas only one IMR flowing mover did so. We defined six 'success factors' and two main future plans, namely development in the current job and stability in their personal life. All of the success factors imply personal responsibility, except for having a sponsor. This was the same for men and women. We did note a difference in self-positioning of men and women, with men positioning themselves more as 'owners' of their career. Finally, we noted how being foreign gave certain particular disadvantages in the institutes, such as language barriers (especially in relation to teaching), isolation (mostly mentioned by women) and lack of a support network outside of the university.

Recruitment and discursive resources:

Overall, comparing the formal criteria and the criteria applied in practice, we conclude that there is overlap, but also significant differences between the formal and the applied criteria in both the IMR and the IMAPP. Differences between the formal criteria in the different documents we analysed and differences between the criteria applied in practice as reported in the appointment reports and interviews were also found. We found that the criteria that are formalized do not all have the same importance when applied in practice. For example, the proven experience in acquiring external project grants (IMAPP formal criterion) or the teaching experience required within the IMR, tend to have some leeway in the actual selection process. The job profiles show the ambition to recruit the 'ideal academic' that has it all, but committee members often have to tune down their demands in practice. We also observed the opposite; criteria being applied in practice that are not emphasised in the job profile. For the postdoc positions in the IMR the interview data showed that publications are considered very important in the selection of postdocs, whereas this is not mentioned in the job descriptions. Thus, formal criteria can be applied selectively, or less strictly. Also, the specific job profile may emphasize some criteria over others. The nature of a vacant position might for example demand experience with a specific research method or extensive teaching experience, which would therefore be of more importance than other criteria. Hence, the formalized criteria do not all carry the same weight. Because dominant criteria can shift and because criteria are in most cases not specified, there is room for interpretation and room to manoeuvre for the selection committees. This points to the relevance of selection committees and their decisive role in recruitment and selection, and nuances the importance of formalization of criteria.

A criterion that turned out to be very important in the actual selection process in both the STEM as SSH field, but is not formalized in the documents, is the personality of the candidate and the behaviour during the job interview. This criterion depends very much on personal preference of and a 'click' with the committee members. If the committee is not aware of possible biases of this criterion, this could disadvantage certain candidates while benefit others. Ideas about personality and presentation in male dominated environment may narrow ideas about suitability of candidates. Research shows that the implicit ideal worker fits men better than women, particularly in male dominated academic environments such as in IMAPP.

The formal criteria in the documents do not often contain the word 'excellence'. When excellence is mentioned, it mainly refers to top publications and success in acquiring prestigious, personal prizes, awards, or funding. Within the appointment reports, the word excellence is seldom used to justify the choice for the number one candidate. The interviewees only spoke about excellence when we asked them to explain the difference between a candidate with minimal requirements and a really excellent candidate. The results show that excellence is neither a strictly formalized criterion, nor part of the discourse of committee members.

We noticed some clear differences between the institutes in relation to gender and gender awareness. Within the IMAPP, gender means the number of women staff. Both the formal documents as well as the committee members explicitly pay attention to the lack of women staff within the research institute. At the moment of writing report 7.1, there was one female professor and one female assistant professor among the permanent staff. Although there is an aim to change the low number of women in the staff, this is not effectuated in the appointment of women candidates, as in every procedure men candidates are preferred over women candidates. There is no recognition or awareness of gender processes in the recruitment and selection process or in the construction of criteria.

Within the IMR, the number of women academics is much higher than within the IMAPP. It could be that because of the increased number of women staff compared to earlier years, some committee members think that nowadays gender plays less of a role in the IMR than it used to do in the past. Within the IMR, gender also means the number of women staff, in sections where few women are employed. Committee members argued that because of the low number of women staff in their section, women tend to have an advantage in the selection procedure. However, in IMR other meanings of gender are also present. A number of women committee members pointed towards the pervasive role gender can play in the selection of candidates. They gave examples of how women are evaluated differently compared to men and how feminine characteristics, such as women being too modest, can hamper a positive evaluation for women candidates. So some of the committee members are aware of gender processes in the recruitment and selection process but others are not. Similar to the IMAPP, there seems no recognition or awareness of gender processes in the construction of criteria within the IMR.

Organisational features/modalities:

In the report 5.1 we focus on the governance and financial management of the Radboud University at large and of the particular institutes of the Institute for Mathematics, Astrophysics and Particle Physics (STEM) and the Institute for Management Research (SSH) in relation to gender.

At the University level attention is given to gender and broader diversity in the strategic plan and the HR agenda for the next five years. The strategic plan only speaks broadly of diversity and the intention to increase the (gender-based) diversity of full professors at the university. The diversity policy is mostly placed under the umbrella of HR, as the HR agenda is much more elaborate on the diversity/gender policies of the universities. Both plans speak

more of diversity in a broad sense- including also international diversity – than of gender equality. Target figures are set for the coming years regarding women and men full professors, as well as several measures to be taken (e.g., tenure track system).

The composition of decision making bodies- Executive Board, Board of Governance, Financial departments, Faculty Boards, different works councils – are not always gender balanced but women are present in all of them. Decision making is done within the structure of the yearly university policy cycle. It is for a large part top-down, but structural room is built for employee participation on both faculty and university level.

The budgeting system of the university as a whole is not completely transparent. A very small part of the budget goes into the general diversity policy. The same goes for the institutes' budgeting processes: part of the budgeting processes is not transparent, but both institutes do allocate some small parts of the budget to gender-sensitive items such as a gender research group in IMR and measures to attract more women students in IMAPP.

Regarding the conditions for an academic career we can conclude that the IMR is focused on the internal organisation and standardization of PhD candidates. The IMAPP is more outward looking, as it has no central doctoral school but allocates PhD candidates to national discipline-related doctoral schools. The student-staff ratio shows the different orientations of the two institutes, with the IMR being education-focused and the IMAPP being research-focused. This is also reflected in the number of fixed-term contracts, which comprise one-third in the IMR and about half in the IMAPP (going for a large part to postdocs).

Within IMR (no data available from IMAPP) we noticed a gender and functional segregation concerning research points: full professors (men and women) earned the most points in 2013, whereas women early career academics earned the least. This decreases the latter groups' chances of continuing in academia and climbing the academic ladder in comparison to their male counterparts.

The evaluation system is standardized through mandatory annual performance interviews. In these interviews no topics revolve around gender or discrimination.

The salary system is also standardized. For this reason, no remarkable differences regarding salary scales exist concerning men and women in same positions in the IMAPP (in 2013). We do not have information about differences between women and men within those scales.

Vignette 6: Switzerland – University of Lausanne

Switzerland – University of Lausanne

Overall Characteristics: Masculine habitus, co-optation logic (but with women's supportive mentoring programme), work/life imbalance declared, depending on couple.

Three other main characteristics define the Swiss 'academic pipeline'. First, it's a pipeline that picks up a very international flux of students. Second, this pipeline has a really narrow bottleneck (i.e. the chances of being stabilized are really thin), especially for women owing to the Swiss gender regime. Third, this specific pipeline 'leaks' in a potentially highly buoyant extra-academic labour market.

Gender and Welfare Regimes:

Modified male breadwinner models, while females have reached almost equal percentage, but part-times and extended leaves upon maternity and motherhood; federal states.

This brief overview of available data would suggest that the barriers to women's equal access to a successful academic career are still quite numerous in the Swiss National & Local Policy Report context, despite the adoption of wide-ranging and relatively well-funded equal opportunity measures. The dominant Swiss gender regime is characterised by increasing activity rates across all age and educational groups of women, but also by some of the highest levels of women's part-time working, particularly amongst mothers of young children. In addition to this typically female working pattern, the division of domestic labour and unpaid care activities is particularly unequal; with women taking responsibility for almost 80% of daily household chores. This "modified male breadwinner" gender regime is bolstered by a number of structural characteristics of Swiss society: very low levels of childcare provision, extremely expensive childcare costs, high levels of horizontal and vertical segregation, a relatively large gender pay gap, particularly at the upper reaches of the occupational hierarchy.

It is particularly notable that the small progression achieved in women's access to an academic career over the past 10 years has tended to benefit women of foreign nationality rather than their Swiss counterparts.

Previous and existing gender policy: Strong, mentoring programme and docs' promotion/support programmes (however not postdoc), supportive of Garcia research project, support of application processes, perhaps quota for women

Quantitative Data: Leaky pipeline, glass ceiling, sticky floor, postdoc bottleneck

The interpretation of statistical and survey data on PhD holders presented in previous sections pinpointed by some theoretical thoughts indubitably corroborate the presence of leaky pipeline phenomenon in science at the national level; a clear picture of vertical gender segregation in academic career paths of the PhD holders. However, on the level of individual STEM/SSH departments, this picture is not so uniquely expressed—it shows that the reality is far more complex. However, accessible evidences enable a conclusion that a specific masculine academic culture,

which is mirrored at different levels of scientific endeavours, is preventing more or less in every scientific discipline equal representation of women at more 'prestigious' stages and positions of scientific career. Moreover, what can be done to overpass the influence and agency of this particular culture?

In the world of politics, special female quotas have been introduced already some time ago to enforce greater participation, influence and interests of women in this domain. Perhaps the same kind of measure should be enforced and widely introduced in science as well. This idea is not as unusual as it seems at the first glance, since in some way it is already materialising. For example, in the new financial perspective, the European Commission is already encouraging greater involvements of women in science within the Horizon 2014-2020. For this purpose, special evaluation criteria that require consideration of gender perspective in proposed project are set up (e.g. in terms of the content of the research, as well as in terms of the sample construction of observed populations and last but not least in scheduling the composition of research teams, such as involvement of 40 percent of women PhD students into ITN programmes). Similar logic should be applied also into the national calls for tenders, which will enable more gender-balanced composition of research teams. This will permit approaches that are more objective in scientific research through consideration of gender perspective as well. Additionally, the logic of quotas should be considered also in the management of scientific institutions; e.g. in membership of each scientific commissions and boards, where a certain share of women should be secured at the top positions (e.g. dean), and a gender rotation should be carried into effect. The criteria of scientific excellence (guaranteed quotations of females' scientific work) should be also restated and pertinent measures created to make women more visible in their scientific disciplines.

Qualitative Results:

Postdocs:

Interviewees declared that they worked more than full time and were not too critical about this. They generally considered this to be part of the game and were willing to play it this way. A large number of our women interviewees do not seem to see themselves as unable to conform to such a norm. The women post-docs use many strategies to fulfil this norm as nearly as possible. They do so even if such strategies might put them in a very vulnerable situation because of the gender power balance in their couple or the Swiss 'breadwinner' gender regime.

In the Swiss academic context, being mobile clearly appears to be one of the main assets for improving one's chances of achieving a stable academic career. By contrast, the pathways followed by those who do not or cannot move are longer, more chaotic and more contingent because they are more dependent on the occasional and local needs of the departments. Thus, since women (and especially Swiss women, who often are in an unbalanced conjugal situation) are potentially less mobile than men, they are more likely to be hired to less prestigious and more precarious positions.

Newly Tenured:

- And once hired to such positions, their chances of achieving professional stability in the academy diminish considerably.

- The co-optation logic is fundamental to understanding how tenure is achieved. Indeed, since having a mentor (and benefit of his or her social capital) seems to increase the chances of being one day tenured, one can think that the co-optation logic is working within this process. Some women interviewees seem not have benefited from such a co-optation logic. They thus are more likely to be pushed aside from the pool of high-potential candidates. But one must also note that not every woman seems to have been sidelined by such processes. And the ones who benefit from such a transfer of social capital are deeply aware of this issue. Thus, some of them are involved in one of the many mentoring programs for women organized at the UNIL.

- Women working in research institutions are more likely to declare, especially among Swiss women interviewees, that they experience temporal and mental tensions between their commitments to their work and to their family life. At an individual and micro level, the intensity of the tension around work-life balance strongly depends on gender-role arrangement with the partner. When their gender-role repartition is egalitarian or inverted, women are less likely to experience work-life balance issues as a source of tension. 'Egalitarian' or 'inverted' configurations are pretty difficult to maintain because of the structural organization of the work-life balance in Switzerland (and especially the lack of childcare facilities).

Movers/Leavers:

Reasons for leaving: Publishing was self-imposed: the deadlines, the targeted number of publications, and the discipline to work on articles. Interviewees thus internalized this pressure. The general sense was also that having the freedom to do what one wants research-wise is important for one's career. Yet, the other side of the coin here was no real embeddedness in the faculty.

Recruitment and discursive resources:

Firstly, not all the (quite numerous) post-doc positions in the Swiss academic system automatically lead to those positions associated with a tenure track opportunity, or a stable academic career. A lot of the academic research (and a smaller proportion of teaching) currently taking place in Switzerland is funded externally, on the basis of competitive research procedures. This implies that only a small proportion of the male and female post-docs who contribute to these externally funded research projects, through a succession of fixed-term, sometimes part-time, post-doc positions, will ever gain access to a stable academic career.

Secondly, in the face of increased (international) competition for tenure track positions, the UNIL has significantly increased the pressure on its' Faculties to formalise their selection procedures and to promote gender equality in

recruitment. Although there is rhetorical respect for disciplinary specificities in the choice of indicators, the formal criteria for access to tenure track positions appear to be very similar across the SHS and STEM Faculties. They are available to all members of the academic community and are presented regularly to graduate students at all stages of their PhD completion (and more explicitly to women, through a number of highly visible mentoring schemes and dedicated funding programmes). To a certain extent, there is a shared feeling the “everyone knows what you have to do to continue working in the academy after a PhD”. What’s more, these requirements are relatively similar across the Faculties and disciplines.

Thirdly, although there is almost no explicit reference to “excellence” in any of the official documents studied (either at HR or Faculty level), they nevertheless provide a description of the idealised academic profile, which is thought to be well suited to an increasingly international and competitive environment. This ideal-type figure could be described as the well-rounded academic, who is expected to “perform” equally well in research (by attracting competitive external funding - notably to keep the post-docs in employment -, and publishing in the top international, peer-reviewed journals), in teaching (by attracting high quality graduate students), and in maintaining high levels of “organisational wellbeing” (particularly by taking on administrative duties). In addition, this (imaginary) figure of academic equilibrium should know how to set aside time for non-academic activities (leisure, sport, culture, even family-life...). In both Faculties, this ideal figure is symbolically opposed to a number of negative images, most of which centre on the “one-dimensional professor”, who neglects his (not usually her) teaching and management duties to focus exclusively on his or her “research output” (or H-index). Finally, the discourse of “excellence” appears to take on quite negative connotations in both the SHS and STEM Faculties. More precisely, it is a critical evaluation of the criteria on which excellence could or should be judged that is shared by our interviewees. This enables them to justify the introduction of “subjective” selection criteria into the early-career selection procedures and to reject the sole use of bibliometric or financial performance measures. These indicators are not presented as unimportant. In practice, they are often used to reach a “short list” of prospective candidates and are presented as perfectly legitimate tools at this stage of the selection process. It is after this first “sifting” exercise that they become redundant and that more “qualitative” indicators are sought.

At this stage of our research, it is difficult to determine the gendered consequences of the emergence of the figure of the well-rounded academic in the Swiss context. We know from experience that the use of quantifiable performance indicators and the adoption of more formalised recruitment procedures are usually favourable to under-represented groups, including women. At the same time, previous research has suggested that a strong focus on research productivity indicators and the promotion of geographical mobility through international career paths are not conducive to women’s academic careers. In our case study, it could be that attempts to broaden the criteria on which post-doc candidates are judged, beyond metric research performance indicators, will prove to be more favourable to women applicants. On the other hand, if the critical attitude we have identified towards existing indicators of “academic excellence” simply leads to a blurring of recruitment criteria and to the legitimisation of “subjective impressions” as to who would (or would not) be a “good match”, female candidates may not necessarily benefit from this potential shift in the dominant academic ethos.

These are questions we hope to explore further with the data collected for the GARCIA project.

Organisational features/modalities: University is embedded in the international market, university not as attractive for employment, despite being regionally strongly embedded in Cantons.

We presented in this report an overview of the financial, management and decision-making bodies of the UNIL and of two faculties (SSP and FBM). First, we can stress that women are underrepresented at the top of the hierarchy within the UNIL and within each of the faculties studied here. Women are nevertheless present at each level and the rectorate of the UNIL is committed to changing this situation through its “strategic action plan”. Secondly, because some data (on employees for instance) is not in the public domain, we faced significant difficulties in finding data on budgets and funding at the Faculty level. From this point of view, the financial decision-making processes within the UNIL appear to be somewhat opaque. Finally, even though there is an evaluation system in place, academic productivity doesn’t have any impact on the wages of the academic staff, which are fixed and standardized by an independent public-sector pay scale. Because of this scale, there is no difference in earnings between men and women when they are hired for the same position.

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